

Post factum analysis in TOPSIS based decision making method

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Abstract

TOPSIS (Technique of Order Preference by Similarity to Ideal Solution) is a popular decision-making technique used to rank a discrete set of alternatives based on the premise that a good alternative should simultaneously have the shortest distance from a positive ideal solution and the farthest distance from a negative ideal solution. Sometimes, ambiguity or impreciseness in the decision information may lead a decision maker to raise questions about the robustness of the recommendation of a TOPSIS based decision-making model. To address the concerns of the decision maker, this paper therefore proposes a sensitivity and stability analysis framework to address the robustness of the recommendations and the different achievable targets set by the decision maker. Specifically, we analyze the effect of a change in the rating of an alternative under a criterion and determine the appropriate conditions to predict how the closeness coefficients change. Through this analysis, we investigate the minimal performance change that is required in an alternative's rating under a criterion to achieve a particular target set by decision maker when the rest of the decision information set remains unaltered. An algorithm is provided to find the set of criteria whereby changing a criterion of a alternative, it can obtain another alternative's rank. We investigate the behaviour of the closeness coefficient of an alternative when a criterion rating changes, and provide two algorithms to identify the upper and lower-rank achievable alternatives. Subsequently, we describe the rank reversal of a pair of alternatives and introduce the concept of a rank sensitive interval. A numerical example on university ranking is provided to demonstrate the validity of the proposed model.

Keywords: TOPSIS, Post factum analysis, Sensitivity analysis, Rank reversal

1. Introduction

Often times, decision making involves multiple perspectives on assessing the courses of action (Greco et al., 2010). These perspectives usually form the evaluation criteria which is mapped to a value function. Generally, for such a class of multi-criteria decision making (MCDM) problems, we consider the evaluation of a finite set of actions under a family of criteria to determine the best action or to rank order the actions

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from best to worst (Zopounidis & Doumpos, 2002). To help the decision makers to solve this class of problems, a suite of methods have been proposed e.g., AHP (Saaty, 1980), TOPSIS (Hwang & Yoon, 1981), PROMETHEE (Brans, 1982), ELECTRE (Roy, 1968), QUALIFLEX (Paelinck, 1978), MULTIMOORA (Brauers & Zavadskas, 2010), and VIKOR (Opricovic, 1998). An exhaustive set of methods with their selection criteria in the context of the decision making scenarios has been illustrated in a recent study (Wątróbski et al., 2018). They have also been employed to solve a wide range of practical problems in engineering, technology, economics, management, and other allied areas (Hwang & Yoon, 1981; Figueira et al., 2005; Tzeng & Huang, 2011).

The Technique of Order Preference by Similarity to Ideal Solution (TOPSIS) is a popular MCDM method for ranking the alternatives (Hwang & Yoon, 1981). It has been reported that TOPSIS is the most popular method after the Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) (Zavadskas et al., 2016; Zyoud & Fuchs-Hanusch, 2017). The popularity of TOPSIS is attributed to its simplicity and logical foundation. The key advantages of the TOPSIS procedure were identified by Kim et al. (1997) and Shih et al. (2007) as follows: 1) a strong logical foundation that simulates the rationale of human choice; 2) a scalar value that treats the best and the worst alternatives simultaneously; 3) a simple step-wise computational procedure, which can be readily mounted on a spreadsheet. These advantages encourage the application of TOPSIS in solving practical decision making problems as compared to the other MCDM methods (Zanakis et al., 1998; Behzadian et al., 2012; Zyoud & Fuchs-Hanusch, 2017).

TOPSIS has five steps: 1) normalization of the decision matrix; 2) construction of the weighted normalized decision matrix; 3) determination of the positive and negative ideal solutions; 4) computation of a separation measure; 5) computation of the relative closeness to the ideal solution. Many investigations have been made regarding each of the steps of TOPSIS (Olson, 2004; Opricovic & Tzeng, 2004; Zavadskas et al., 2006; Hu et al., 2016). For instance, Olson (2004) analyzed the effect of different weighting schemes and different distance metrics in TOPSIS. Zavadskas et al. (2006) analyzed the ranking accuracy in TOPSIS under the vector and linear scale normalization methods. Kuo (2017) analyzed the issue in the closeness coefficient and proposed some modifications to achieve more accurate results. Using the loss aversion concept of behavioural economics, Yoon & Kim (2017) proposed a modified TOPSIS method in which a value function has been constructed on the basis of the loss aversion ratio to rank the alternatives. Dwivedi et al. (2018) have modified the closeness coefficient by incorporating a set of weights associated with the distance from the positive and negative ideal solutions.

Shih et al. (2007) extended the TOPSIS method to group decision making. TOPSIS has also been extended to handle different types of decision information represented by interval data (Jahanshahloo et al., 2006), fuzzy numbers (Wang & Elhag, 2006), intuitionistic fuzzy values (Boran et al., 2009), hesitant fuzzy set (Xu & Zhang, 2013), interval type-2 fuzzy numbers (Chen & Lee, 2010), and other variants of fuzzy sets (Wu et al., 2018; Liang & Xu, 2017; Han et al., 2018). Lourenzutti & Krohling (2016) proposed a generalization of the TOPSIS method in a group setting with heterogeneous decision information, which

they refer to as the group modular random TOPSIS (GRM-TOPSIS). GRM-TOPSIS is well suited to deal with situations, in which each decision maker has the flexibility to independently define the criteria set, the weight vector, the factors that may affect the alternatives' ratings, and the type of information the decision maker wants to use for each criterion.

In TOPSIS, two types of decision information are required to find the rank of the alternatives. One is the decision matrix whose entries are the ratings of different alternatives under different criteria and the other one is the weight information of the criteria. The criteria set may be qualitative, quantitative, or a mix of both qualitative and quantitative attributes. This decision information is mostly given by the decision maker. The measurement of the qualitative criteria depends solely on the decision maker's subjective judgement, such as the feel of driving a fast car. The quantitative criteria may link directly to an alternative specification, such as the speed of the car as stated by its specification or the decision maker's judgement if we present the data on the speed of a car to the decision maker and ask him/her to rate it using new scales. As the decision maker is the main source of the decision information, ambiguity may arise in the input information, leading to possible variability and imprecision in the final decision outcome. Therefore, there is a need to analyse the recommendation generated from the TOPSIS algorithm to ensure the robustness of the recommendation.

While there have been numerous studies to analyze the steps of TOPSIS and to deal with the types of uncertainty in the performance evaluation of the alternatives, scant attention has been paid to the post analysis of the recommendation from TOPSIS, with respect to the information given. This is particularly so for the sensitivity or stability of the ranking order of the alternatives with respect to the weight information or the decision information. Li et al. (2013) studied the sensitivity of the final rank ordering with respect to the weights' information. Taking uniform initial weights of the criteria, they designed fourteen schema to investigate the sensitivity of the rank order to the variation in each weight. They derived the theoretical range of the variation of each weight needed to hold the rank order of the alternatives fixed. Song & Chung (2016) conducted a post recommendation analysis for TOPSIS based on Triantaphyllou & Sánchez (1997)'s sensitivity analysis and suggestion in order to assess the effect of uncertainty in determining the most critical criterion and performance measures. Simulation or scenario based analysis has also been conducted to investigate the sensitivity of the weights' information over the final recommendation of TOPSIS (e.g. Azimifard et al. (2018); Jayasooriya et al. (2018); Baležentis & Streimikiene (2017); Song & Chung (2016)). Maliene et al. (2018) used simulation and sensitivity analysis to show that the dispersion of the relative importance values of the alternatives correlate with the Euclidean distances of the aggregated values and concluded that the dispersion of the relative importance values contributes directly to ranking uncertainty.

From previous studies, robustness or sensitivity analysis of TOPSIS is limited to the weights' information, much of which point to whether variances exist in the recommendations, without any explicit information related to the robustness of the results. As a sensitivity analysis of the subjective weights' information is useful, the impreciseness or ambiguity in the decision information and their impact on the final results warrant further study in robust decision analysis. Further, the lack of a systematic analysis of the recommendation

generated from TOPSIS in the presence of ambiguity in the decision information presents a reliability concern in the final outcomes. These facts thus motivate us to analyze the post recommendation of TOPSIS considering the various perspectives of the decision analysis.

In this paper, we develop a framework to analyse the recommendation from TOPSIS and a decision maker's viewpoints. As the starting point of the proposed methodology is the initial recommendation from TOPSIS and the interaction of the decision maker, we label the proposed methodology as a *post factum analysis* of TOPSIS following the study of Kadziński et al. (2016), where it has been argued that the knowledge about the different consequences of the decision information provided may stimulate more questions from the decision maker. For example, after gleaning the initial recommendation on the rank order from TOPSIS, a decision maker may wonder how the improvement or change of an alternative's performance under a criterion influences the initial recommendation. Further, the decision maker may be interested to know the range of an alternative's performance under a criterion in which an improvement or deterioration from the initial level does not change the initial recommendation. Addressing such questions on the initial recommendation will allow one to design a robust and reliable decision-making framework based on TOPSIS.

Specifically, our post factum analysis framework of TOPSIS seeks to answer the decision maker's questions concerning the robustness of a recommendation or different achievable targets under the assumption that the weights of the criteria are known and are perfectly elicited in the decision making. Thus, we focus on answering the decision maker's questions related to the robustness based on the variation of the alternatives' performance under different criteria. In general, the proposed post factum analysis framework seeks to address the following research questions related to the recommendation of TOPSIS and its robustness:

- under what conditions will an alternative's closeness coefficient improve, when changing its rating under a criterion without affecting the other alternatives' ratings and closeness coefficients?
- what is the behaviour of the closeness coefficient of an alternative to the change of its rating under a criterion when all other information remain unaltered?
- how much change is required in the rating of an alternative under a particular criterion to achieve another alternative's ranking?
- by changing an alternative's rating under a criterion, which higher or lower rank alternatives are achieved by the alternative?
- how can the rank of a pair of alternatives be reversed without affecting the other alternatives' rank order?
- what is the rank sensitive interval of an alternative's rating under a criterion. i.e. how to find the interval of an alternative's rating under a criterion such that when the alternative's rating varies, the overall rank order of the alternatives is still the initial rank order of the alternatives found through TOPSIS?

Addressing the above issues presents a better understanding of the dynamics of the TOPSIS based decision-making approach and helps to generate more robust recommendations. Our analysis follows the earlier sensitivity analysis works on MCDM (Wolters & Mareschal, 1995; Triantaphyllou & Sanchez, 1997). However, it is not limited to identifying the critical criteria or finding the improvement in the performance of an alternative under a criterion to achieve the first rank. Rather, it tries to shed light on the broad spectrum of a decision maker’s concerns on the initial recommendation generated by TOPSIS. In short, we obtain a rich perspective of the decision results that not only provide a deeper insight into the decision analysis but also an overview of the possible consequences.

To do this, we organize the paper as follows. Section 2 describes the steps of the standard TOPSIS method. In Section 3, we analyze the effects of a change in the rating of an alternative under a criterion and obtain the appropriate conditions to predict the change in the closeness coefficients. Further, we investigate the amount of change required in an alternative’s rating under a criterion to achieve the rank of a desired alternative. An algorithm is applied to find the set of criteria in which changing any of them would allow the alternative to achieve another alternative’s rank. Next, we analyze the behaviour of the closeness coefficient of an alternative with respect to the change of its rating under a criterion and provide two algorithms for identifying the upper- and lower-rank achievable alternatives. Based on this analysis, in Section 4, we propose an algorithm for reversing the rank of any pair of alternatives. In Section 5, we illustrate a way of finding the rank sensitive interval for an alternative’s rating under a criterion and provide an algorithm to compute the rank sensitive interval. Section 6 presents a numerical example to demonstrate the validity of the proposed model while Section 7 concludes the paper.

2. TOPSIS

TOPSIS was first presented by Hwang & Yoon (1981). Since then, it has been applied widely to solve many practical MCDM problems and has emerged as a popular MCDM method ((Zyoud & Fuchs-Hanusch, 2017; Zanakis et al., 1998; Behzadian et al., 2012)).

TOPSIS ranks the alternatives based on the idea of a compromise solution. In other words, TOPSIS helps a decision maker to select the alternative which should have the shortest distance from a positive ideal solution (PIS) and the farthest distance from a negative ideal solution (NIS) (Hwang & Yoon, 1981).

TOPSIS requires two forms of information from the user to rank a decision alternative. One is the decision information (often labelled as a decision matrix) of the alternatives against a predefined set of performance criteria. The other information form is the relative importance of the criteria. Mathematically, the description of the decision information and weights’ information is as follows:

- A finite set of $m(\geq 2)$ alternatives: $A = \{A_i | i \in I\}$, where $I = \{1, 2, \dots, m\}$
- A fixed set of criteria: $C = \{C_j | j \in J\}$ where $J = \{1, 2, \dots, n\}$
- The weight vector of the criteria: $w = (w_1, w_2, \dots, w_n)$ such that $w_j \geq 0$ and $\sum_{j=1}^n w_j = 1$.

- The alternatives are assessed over the criteria and the evaluations are summarized in the following decision matrix:

$$D = \begin{matrix} & C_1 & C_2 & \cdots & C_n \\ A_1 & \left(\begin{matrix} a_{11} & a_{12} & \cdots & a_{1n} \end{matrix} \right) \\ A_2 & \left(\begin{matrix} a_{21} & a_{22} & \cdots & a_{2n} \end{matrix} \right) \\ \vdots & \left(\begin{matrix} \vdots & \vdots & \cdots & \vdots \end{matrix} \right) \\ A_m & \left(\begin{matrix} a_{m1} & a_{m2} & \cdots & a_{mn} \end{matrix} \right) \end{matrix}$$

where a_{ij} denotes the performance measure of alternative A_i against criterion C_j .

With the above information, TOPSIS can rank the alternatives using the following steps:

Step 1 Normalization of decision matrix. In general, different criteria are measured using different scales.

To facilitate the inter-criteria comparison, we use a normalization technique. There are several common normalization techniques used to form the normalized decision matrix, $R = (r_{ij})_{m \times n}$, namely:

- Vector normalization. For the benefit criteria:

$$r_{ij} = \frac{a_{ij}}{\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^m a_{ij}^2}} \quad (1)$$

For cost criteria:

$$r_{ij} = \frac{1/a_{ij}}{\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^m 1/a_{ij}^2}} \quad (2)$$

The drawback is the non-equal scale length

- Linear scale transformation (Max-Min). For the benefit criteria

$$r_{ij} = \frac{a_{ij} - a_j^{\min}}{a_j^{\max} - a_j^{\min}} \quad (3)$$

For the cost criteria

$$r_{ij} = \frac{a_j^{\max} - a_{ij}}{a_j^{\max} - a_j^{\min}} \quad (4)$$

where $a_j^{\max} = \max_i a_{ij}$ and $a_j^{\min} = \min_i a_{ij}$.

- Linear scale transformation (Max). For the benefit criteria

$$r_{ij} = \frac{a_{ij}}{a_j^{\max}} \quad (5)$$

For the cost criteria

$$r_{ij} = 1 - \frac{a_{ij}}{a_j^{\max}} \quad (6)$$

Step 2 Compute the weighted normalized decision matrix. The weighted normalized decision matrix $V = (v_{ij})_{m \times n}$ is computed as follows:

$$v_{ij} = w_j * r_{ij} \text{ for } i = 1, 2, \dots, m, j = 1, 2, \dots, n \quad (7)$$

Step 3 Determine the positive ideal solution (PIS) and negative ideal solution (NIS) respectively:

$$PIS = (v_1^+, v_2^+, \dots, v_n^+), \quad \text{where } v_j^+ = \max_i v_{ij} \quad (8)$$

$$NIS = (v_1^-, v_2^-, \dots, v_n^-), \quad \text{where } v_j^- = \min_i v_{ij}. \quad (9)$$

Step 4 Compute a separation measure based on the n -dimensional Euclidean distance. The separation measure of alternative A_i from PIS is found as follows:

$$D_i^+ = \sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^n (v_{ij} - v_j^+)^2}. \quad (10)$$

Similarly, the separation measure from NIS is computed as follows:

$$D_i^- = \sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^n (v_{ij} - v_j^-)^2}. \quad (11)$$

Step 5 Compute the relative closeness coefficient to the ideal solutions. For an alternative A_i , the relative closeness coefficient is defined as follows:

$$CC_i = \frac{D_i^-}{D_i^+ + D_i^-} \text{ for } i = 1, 2, \dots, m. \quad (12)$$

Step 6 Based on the relative closeness coefficient, the alternatives are ranked. The smaller the value of the relative closeness coefficient, the better is the rank of the alternative.

3. Post factum analysis of TOPSIS

Imprecise knowledge about the decision information may trigger several questions from a decision maker regarding the recommendation from TOPSIS about an alternative's ranking. In particular, a decision maker may be concerned about the robustness of the recommendation and may seek to identify the necessary conditions to keep the recommendations unaltered. Therefore, the key focus in our post factum analysis is to capture and understand such conditions for the stability of the recommendations. Based on these

conditions, we will then attempt to address the various questions a decision maker can make corresponding to a variety of targets to be achieved by the alternatives.

In this section, we discuss several concepts associated with our post factum analysis of TOPSIS. We start by investigating the effect of a change in the decision information over the closeness coefficients.

In TOPSIS, the modification in an alternative's rating against a criterion yields a different impact on the closeness coefficients of the alternatives under different normalization techniques. For example, with vector normalization, a change in an alternative's rating not only affects that alternative's closeness coefficient but also the rest of the alternatives' closeness coefficients. Correspondingly, this makes it difficult to predict the change in the closeness coefficients of the alternatives and thus the effect on the overall ranking of the set of alternatives. However, in the linear scale normalization procedure, in a few cases, a change in the alternative's rating affects all of the other alternatives' closeness coefficients (when the maximum or minimum ratings corresponding to a criterion is changed); in the rest of the time it affects only that particular alternative (if the change does not correspond to a maximum or minimum value of the corresponding criterion). Systematically measuring the effect of different changes in the rating is essential to analyzing the system comprehensively. Such a comprehensive understanding is necessary when responding to a decision maker's queries on a variety of targets to be achieved by the alternatives. Also, this analysis provides different perspectives for the stakeholders to analyze their performance under different attributes. For example, when we rank a group of universities under a predefined set of criteria, a university (as a stakeholder) could be interested to analyze how an improvement on a particular criterion could lift their existing outcomes or how by improving the performance on a certain criteria, the university could achieve a better rank.

3.1. Effect of change in criterion rating

To analyze the effect of a change in the input decision information in a systematic manner, we adopt the simplest way to check the TOPSIS model by investigating the TOPSIS output, i.e. the closeness coefficients, when we vary a piece of input information in the decision matrix D . In short, we modify an alternative's rating under a criterion and identify its effect on the final results.

As mentioned, different normalization methods affect the final results of TOPSIS in different ways. To form the link between the change in an alternative's rating with its closeness coefficients, the linear-scale based normalization appears to be more appealing as it does not affect all of the alternatives' closeness coefficients when modifying an alternatives rating under a criterion. Therefore, we will consider the rating scale of the different criteria. Let $[sc_j^L, sc_j^U]$ be the interval scale to rate the alternatives under the criteria C_j , ($j = 1, 2, \dots, n$), where sc_j^L and sc_j^U are the lower and upper bounds of the scale respectively. If such a scale is not given, then we can derive it directly from the decision matrix D as follows:

$$sc_j^L = \min_i a_{ij} \text{ and } sc_j^U = \max_i a_{ij}, \quad j = 1, 2, \dots, n. \quad (13)$$

Now, we construct two artificial alternatives, namely, F_1 and F_2 such that

$$F_1 = (sc_1^U, sc_2^U, \dots, sc_n^U), \quad (14)$$

$$F_2 = (sc_1^L, sc_2^L, \dots, sc_n^L). \quad (15)$$

We will only consider these two fictitious alternatives with the given alternatives in the normalization step. This idea of the introducing fictitious alternatives in the normalization step was first introduced by García-Cascales & Lamata (2012). The new set of alternatives is thus $A' = A \cup F_1 \cup F_2$.

In the following proposition, we describe the effect of a change in a single criterion of an alternative over all of the alternatives' closeness coefficients under the linear scale max-min transformation.

Proposition 1. Let $\Delta_{i_1 j_1}$ be the change in the i_1 -th alternatives rating against the j_1 's criteria $a_{i_1 j_1}$ such that $sc_j^L \leq a_{i_1 j_1} \pm \Delta_{i_1 j_1} \leq sc_j^U$. Suppose $a_{i_1 j_1} \neq sc_j^L$ and $a_{i_1 j_1} \neq sc_j^U$. Then, the relative closeness coefficients of the alternatives $A' \setminus \{A_{i_1}\}$ (to indicate the set of alternatives A' excluding A_{i_1}) remain unaltered under a linear scale max-min transformation.

Proof. Since $sc_{j_1}^L \leq a_{i_1 j_1} \pm \Delta_{i_1 j_1} \leq sc_{j_1}^U$, the normalization of the decision matrix by the Linear Scale Transformation (Max-Min) does not change the entries of the normalized decision matrix $V = (v_{ij})_{m \times n}$ except $v_{i_1 j_1}$. Now, for $w_{j_1} > 0$, we have $w_{j_1} sc_{j_1}^L \leq w_{j_1} (a_{i_1 j_1} \pm \Delta_{i_1 j_1}) \leq w_{j_1} sc_{j_1}^U$. Therefore, the PIS and NIS values, after modifying the rating $a_{i_1 j_1}$, remain as before. Hence, the relative closeness coefficients of the alternatives' set $A' \setminus \{A_{i_1}\}$ remain unchanged. \square

Remark 1. Proposition 1 provides the bounds of $\Delta_{i_1 j_1}$ where the other alternatives' relative closeness coefficients remain unaltered. In fact, the range of $\Delta_{i_1 j_1}$ is $(a_{i_1 j_1} - sc_{j_1}^L, sc_{j_1}^U - a_{i_1 j_1})$. By varying $\Delta_{i_1 j_1}$ in the interval $(a_{i_1 j_1} - sc_{j_1}^L, sc_{j_1}^U - a_{i_1 j_1})$, we can obtain the values of CC_{i_1} without affecting the other alternatives' closeness coefficients.

Remark 2. Proposition 1 is also valid under the Linear Scale Transformation (Max). But it is not valid for the vector normalization as the vector normalization process affects all the entries corresponding to a criterion. In other words, a change in alternative A_i 's rating against criterion C_j affects the rest of the other alternatives' normalized ratings in the vector normalization procedure.

Example 1. Consider the fighter aircraft selection problem as adopted from Hwang & Yoon (1981). The defence ministry of country Y planned to procure a fleet of fighter aircrafts from a powerful nation, say X. The officials of country X provide the detailed characteristic information of the four models which they have decided to sell to country Y. The airforce analyst team considers the following six criteria: maximum speed (C_1), ferrying speed (C_2), maximum payload (C_3), purchasing cost (C_4), reliability (C_5), and manoeuvrability (C_6). Criterion C_4 is a cost criterion. The rest of the criteria are benefit criteria. After the initial screening, 4 fighter aircrafts are selected for further evaluation. The evaluation of each alternative against the criteria

by defence analyst team are summarized in the following decision matrix:

$$D = \begin{matrix} & C_1 & C_2 & C_3 & C_4 & C_5 & C_6 \\ \begin{matrix} A_1 \\ A_2 \\ A_3 \\ A_4 \end{matrix} & \begin{pmatrix} 2 & 1500 & 20000 & 5.5 & 5 & 9 \\ 2.5 & 2700 & 1800 & 6.5 & 3 & 5 \\ 1.8 & 2000 & 21000 & 4.5 & 7 & 7 \\ 2.2 & 1800 & 20000 & 5 & 5 & 5 \end{pmatrix} \end{matrix}$$

The relative importance of the criteria is given as $w = (0.2, 0.1, 0.1, 0.1, 0.2, 0.3)$. Considering the fictitious alternatives F_1 and F_2 , defined according to Eq. (14), we can write the decision matrix as follows:

$$D = \begin{matrix} & C_1 & C_2 & C_3 & C_4 & C_5 & C_6 \\ \begin{matrix} A_1 \\ A_2 \\ A_3 \\ A_4 \\ F_1 \\ F_2 \end{matrix} & \begin{pmatrix} 2 & 1500 & 20000 & 5.5 & 5 & 9 \\ 2.5 & 2700 & 18000 & 6.5 & 3 & 5 \\ 1.8 & 2000 & 21000 & 4.5 & 7 & 7 \\ 2.2 & 1800 & 20000 & 5 & 5 & 5 \\ 2.5 & 2700 & 21000 & 6.5 & 7 & 9 \\ 1.8 & 1800 & 18000 & 4.5 & 3 & 5 \end{pmatrix} \end{matrix}$$

Now, we implement the TOPSIS algorithm with the Linear Scale Min-Max normalization method. Applying Eqs. (3) and (4), we obtain

$$R = \begin{pmatrix} 0.2857 & 0 & 0.6667 & 0.5000 & 0.5000 & 1.0000 \\ 1.0000 & 1.0000 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0.4167 & 1.0000 & 1.0000 & 1.0000 & 0.5000 \\ 0.5714 & 0.2500 & 0.6667 & 0.7500 & 0.5000 & 0 \\ 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad (16)$$

From Eq. (7), we obtain the weighted normalized decision matrix

$$V = \begin{pmatrix} 0.0571 & 0 & 0.0667 & 0.0500 & 0.1000 & 0.3000 \\ 0.2000 & 0.1000 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0.0417 & 0.1000 & 0.1000 & 0.2000 & 0.1500 \\ 0.1143 & 0.0250 & 0.0667 & 0.0750 & 0.1000 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad (17)$$

The positive and negative ideal solutions are obtained with the help of Eqs. (8) and (9):

$$PIS = (0.2, 0.1, 0.1, 0.1, 0.2, 0.3) \text{ and } NIS = (0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0).$$

The closeness coefficients of the alternatives are as follows: $CC_1 = 0.6127$, $CC_2 = 0.3660$, $CC_3 = 0.5306$, and $CC_4 = 0.3517$. The rank order of the alternatives is $A_1 > A_3 > A_2 > A_4$.

Now, we consider alternative A_4 's rating under the criterion C_5 (entry a_{45} of the decision matrix). Clearly, it is not the maximum or minimum value of the C_5 column (i.e. $a_{45} \neq sc_5^U = 7$ and $a_{45} \neq sc_5^L = 3$) of the decision matrix D . According to Proposition 1, we can change the rating of a_{45} so that it satisfies the following inequality: $3 \leq a_{45} \pm \Delta_{45} \leq 7$, and the other alternatives' closeness coefficients remain unaltered. We set $\Delta_{45} = 1$ and re-evaluate the steps of TOPSIS to find the values of the new closeness coefficients. We obtain the closeness coefficient as follows: $CC_1 = 0.6127$, $CC_2 = 0.3660$, $CC_3 = 0.5306$, and $CC_4 = 0.3964$. Clearly, the closeness coefficient of alternative A_4 has increased while the rest of the other alternatives' closeness coefficients remain the same. This validates our proposition.

3.2. Finding improvement/degradation (Δ_{ij}) to achieve targets

Next, we seek an answer to the following. Is it possible for the i_2 -th alternative to achieve the rank of the i_1 -th alternative by changing its value against a criterion without affecting the other alternatives' closeness coefficients? In short, we are interested to know the amount of $\Delta_{i_2j_1}$ required to change in the i_2 -th alternative's rating under the j_1 -th criterion, i.e. $a_{i_2j_1}$, to achieve the i_1 -th alternative's rank without affecting the other alternatives' closeness coefficients. To emphasize the fact that the change is intended to achieve the i_1 -th alternative's rank, we use the notation $\Delta_{i_2j_1}^{i_1}$ instead of $\Delta_{i_2j_1}$.

Let $r(A_i)$ denote the rank of alternative A_i . Clearly, the smaller the rank, the better is the rank order of the alternative. Without any loss of generality, suppose $r(A_{i_1}) < r(A_{i_2})$ (i.e. the i_1 -th alternative is better ranked than the i_2 -th alternative). Our intention is to improve the rank of A_{i_2} over the rank of A_{i_1} , $r(A_{i_1})$, by changing A_{i_2} under the j_1 -th criterion without affecting any of the other alternatives' closeness coefficients. Let $\Delta_{i_2j_1}^{i_1}$ be the change in the rating of the i_2 -th alternative's j_1 -th criterion, $a_{i_2j_1}$, and $CC_{i_2}^{new}$ be the closeness coefficient of A_{i_2} respectively. To keep the other alternatives' closeness coefficient unchanged, we assume that $a_{i_2j_1} \neq sc_{j_1}^L$ and $a_{i_2j_1} \neq sc_{j_1}^U$. Clearly, the rank of A_{i_2} will be better than the rank of A_{i_1} if $CC_{i_2}^{new} > CC_{i_1}$. Let $D_{i_2}^{new-}$ and $D_{i_2}^{new+}$ be the new distances of the i_2 -th alternative from the NIS and PIS, respectively. Therefore,

$$CC_{i_2}^{new} = \frac{D_{i_2}^{new-}}{D_{i_2}^{new-} + D_{i_2}^{new+}} > CC_{i_1}. \quad (18)$$

We can rewrite Eq. (18) as

$$(D_{i_2}^{new-})^2 > \left(\frac{CC_{i_1}}{1 - CC_{i_1}}\right)^2 (D_{i_2}^{new+})^2. \quad (19)$$

Since only the (i_2, j_1) -th entry of the weighted normalized decision matrix V is modified (say $v'_{i_2j_1}$) due to a change in the (i_2, j_1) -th entry of D and the rest of the entries remain unaltered, Eq. (19) can be written

in terms of the entries of V as follows:

$$\sum_{\substack{j=1 \\ j \neq j_1}}^n (v_{i_2j} - NIS_j)^2 + (v'_{i_2j_1} - NIS_{j_1})^2 > k \left(\sum_{\substack{j=1 \\ j \neq j_1}}^n (v_{i_2j} - PIS_j)^2 + (v'_{i_2j_1} - PIS_{j_1})^2 \right) \quad (20)$$

where $k = \left(\frac{CC_{i_1}}{1 - CC_{i_1}} \right)^2$.

Without any loss of generality, suppose C_{j_1} is the benefit criteria. Then, from Eq. (3), we have

$$\begin{aligned} v'_{i_2j_1} &= w_{j_1} \frac{a_{i_2j_1} + \Delta_{i_2j_1}^{i_1} - sc_{j_1}^L}{sc_{j_1}^U - sc_{j_1}^L} \\ &= v_{i_2j_1} + w_{j_1} \frac{\Delta_{i_2j_1}^{i_1}}{sc_{j_1}^U - sc_{j_1}^L} \\ &= v_{i_2j_1} + \frac{w_{j_1}}{l_{j_1}} \Delta_{i_2j_1}^{i_1} \end{aligned} \quad (21)$$

where $l_{j_1} = sc_{j_1}^U - sc_{j_1}^L$.

From Eqs. (20) and (21), we obtain

$$\left(v_{i_2j_1} + \frac{w_{j_1}}{l_{j_1}} \Delta_{i_2j_1}^{i_1} - NIS_{j_1} \right)^2 - k \left(v_{i_2j_1} + \frac{w_{j_1}}{l_{j_1}} \Delta_{i_2j_1}^{i_1} - PIS_{j_1} \right)^2 > \quad (22)$$

$$k \sum_{\substack{j=1 \\ j \neq j_1}}^n (v_{i_2j} - PIS_j)^2 - \sum_{\substack{j=1 \\ j \neq j_1}}^n (v_{i_2j} - NIS_j)^2.$$

The quadratic expression in $\Delta_{i_2j_1}^{i_1}$ can be put in standard form as follows:

$$a(\Delta_{i_2j_1}^{i_1})^2 + b\Delta_{i_2j_1}^{i_1} + c > p \quad (23)$$

where, $a = (w_{j_1}/l_{j_1})^2(1-k)$, $b = 2(w_{j_1}/l_{j_1})(v_{i_2j_1} - NIS_{j_1} - k(v_{i_2j_1} - PIS_{j_1}))$, $c = (v_{i_2j_1} - NIS_{j_1})^2 - k(v_{i_2j_1} - PIS_{j_1})^2$ and $p = \sum_{\substack{j=1 \\ j \neq j_1}}^n (v_{i_2j} - PIS_j)^2 - \sum_{\substack{j=1 \\ j \neq j_1}}^n (v_{i_2j} - NIS_j)^2$.

Now, we utilize the fact that $x^2 > a$ if $x > \sqrt{a}$ and $x < -\sqrt{a}$ to obtain the values of $\Delta_{i_2j_1}^{i_1}$ for which Eq. (23) holds and find the following restrictions:

$$\Delta_{i_2j_1}^{i_1} > -\frac{b}{2a} + \sqrt{\frac{p}{a} + \frac{b^2}{4a^2} - \frac{c}{a}} \quad (24)$$

$$\Delta_{i_2j_1}^{i_1} < -\frac{b}{2a} - \sqrt{\frac{p}{a} + \frac{b^2}{4a^2} - \frac{c}{a}}. \quad (25)$$

From Eqs. (24) and (25), we have the range of values of $\Delta_{i_2j_1}^{i_1}$ but it is not clear whether it is feasible or not. Therefore, we check on the feasibility conditions first. As the ratings of the alternatives under the different criteria are real values, $\Delta_{i_2j_1}^{i_1}$ must be real and that can be seen from the sign of the expression

$\frac{p}{a} + \frac{b^2}{4a^2} - \frac{c}{a}$. If $\frac{p}{a} + \frac{b^2}{4a^2} - \frac{c}{a} < 0$, then there is no real value of $\Delta_{i_2j_1}^{i_1}$ which can allow us to obtain a rank better than A_{i_1} from alternative A_{i_2} by changing the j_1 -th criterion rating of alternative A_{i_2} . In other words, it is not possible to obtain alternative A_{i_1} 's current rank from alternative A_{i_2} under criterion j_1 .

With $\frac{p}{a} + \frac{b^2}{4a^2} - \frac{c}{a} > 0$, this ensures that there are real values for $\Delta_{i_2j_1}^{i_1}$ satisfying Eqs. (24) and (25). So, we only need to check the feasibility condition defined in Proposition 1. Suppose $\beta_1 = -\frac{b}{2a} + \sqrt{\frac{p}{a} + \frac{b^2}{4a^2} - \frac{c}{a}} + \epsilon$, where $\epsilon > 0$. The value of ϵ is chosen such that we can clearly make a distinction between $C_{i_2}^{new}$ and C_{i_1} . It is noted that $\Delta_{i_2j_1}^{i_1} = \beta_1$ satisfies the constraints given in Eq. (24). We now check the condition $sc_{j_1}^L \leq a_{i_1j_1} + \beta_1 \leq sc_{j_1}^U$. If it is satisfied, then the value of $\Delta_{i_2j_1} = \beta_1$ is the required amount of change that we need to make in the j_1 -th criterion rating of alternative A_{i_2} to achieve the ranking of alternative A_{i_1} . If $\Delta_{i_2j_1}^{i_1}$ does not meet the feasibility condition $sc_{j_1}^L < a_{i_1j_1} + \beta_1 < sc_{j_1}^U$, we have no feasible solution for Eq. (24). Similarly, we check the feasibility condition for Eq. (25) by setting $\beta_2 = -\frac{b}{2a} - \sqrt{\frac{p}{a} + \frac{b^2}{4a^2} - \frac{c}{a}} - \epsilon$. If both β_1 and β_2 satisfy the feasibility condition, then based on the signs and magnitudes of β_1 and β_2 , we choose the smaller of β_1 and β_2 .

By the above analysis, we summarize the value of finding $\Delta_{i_2j_1}^{i_1}$ for achieving the rank of the desired alternative by changing a specified criteria in the following proposition:

Proposition 2. The minimum change required to achieve alternative A_{i_1} 's current rank with alternative A_{i_2} ($r(A_{i_1}) < r(A_{i_2})$) making the change $\Delta_{i_2j_1}^{i_1}$ in the j_1 -th criterion without affecting the rest of the alternatives' closeness coefficients is given by

$$\Delta_{i_2j_1}^{i_1} = \begin{cases} \min(\beta_1, \beta_2) & \text{if } a_{i_1j_1} + \{\beta_1, \beta_2\} \in [sc_{j_1}^L, sc_{j_1}^U] \text{ \&} \\ & \beta_1, \beta_2 > 0 \\ \max(\beta_1, \beta_2) & \text{if } a_{i_1j_1} + \{\beta_1, \beta_2\} \in [sc_{j_1}^L, sc_{j_1}^U] \text{ \&} \\ & sgn(\beta_1)sgn(\beta_2) = -1 \\ \beta_1 & \text{if } a_{i_1j_1} + \beta_1 \in [sc_{j_1}^L, sc_{j_1}^U] \\ \beta_2 & \text{if } a_{i_1j_1} + \beta_1 \in [sc_{j_1}^L, sc_{j_1}^U] \end{cases} \quad (26)$$

subject to the feasibility condition $\frac{p}{a} + \frac{b^2}{4a^2} - \frac{c}{a} > 0$, and $a_{i_2j_1} \neq sc_{j_1}^L$ and $a_{i_2j_1} \neq sc_{j_1}^U$. Here, $sgn(x)$ returns 1 or -1 according to the condition $x > 0$ or $x < 0$.

In the above analysis, we have assumed that $r(A_{i_1}) < r(A_{i_2})$. When $r(A_{i_1}) > r(A_{i_2})$ in Eqs. (24) and (25), the signs of the inequalities are reversed and the rest of the results remain unchanged. Now, we provide an algorithm for checking whether it is possible to obtain the rank of A_{i_1} by changing A_{i_2} 's rating under the j_1 -th criterion. The steps of the algorithms are summarized as follows:

Example 2. We apply Algorithm 1 on the data of Example 1. It is clear that alternative A_4 is ranked 4-th. Now, we assess if it is possible to obtain the rank of alternative A_2 from A_4 through changing the rating of A_4 under criterion C_5 and if possible, determine how much change is required in A_4 's current rating

Algorithm 1: Find $\Delta_{i_2 j_1}^{i_1}$

Input : Decision matrix D , weight vector w , i_2 , i_1 , and j_1

Output: required change in i_2 -th alternative under criterion j_1

```
1 if  $\frac{p}{a} + \frac{b^2}{4a^2} - \frac{c}{a} > 0$  then
2    $\beta_1 = -\frac{b}{2a} + \sqrt{\frac{p}{a} + \frac{b^2}{4a^2} - \frac{c}{a} + \epsilon}$ 
3    $\beta_2 = -\frac{b}{2a} - \sqrt{\frac{p}{a} + \frac{b^2}{4a^2} - \frac{c}{a} - \epsilon}$ 
4   if  $a_{i_1 j_1} + \{\beta_1, \beta_2\} \in [sc_{j_1}^L, sc_{j_1}^U]$  then
5     if  $sgn(\beta_1)sgn(\beta_2) = 1$  then
6       return  $\Delta_{i_2 j_1}^{i_1} = \min(|\beta_1|, |\beta_2|)$ 
7     else if  $sgn(\beta_1)sgn(\beta_2) = -1$  &  $r(A_{i_1}) < r(A_{i_2})$  then
8       return  $\Delta_{i_2 j_1}^{i_1} = \max(\beta_1, \beta_2)$ 
9     else
10      |  $\Delta_{i_2 j_1}^{i_1} = \min(\beta_1, \beta_2)$ 
11    end
12  else if  $a_{i_1 j_1} + \beta_1 \in [sc_{j_1}^L, sc_{j_1}^U]$  then
13    | return  $\Delta_{i_2 j_1}^{i_1} = \beta_1$ ;
14  else if  $a_{i_1 j_1} + \beta_2 \in [sc_{j_1}^L, sc_{j_1}^U]$  then
15    | return  $\Delta_{i_2 j_1}^{i_1} = \beta_2$ ;
16  else
17    | Return Not possible to achieve the rank of  $A_{i_1}$  by  $A_{i_2}$ ;
18  end
19 else
20 | Return Not possible to achieve the rank of  $A_{i_1}$  by  $A_{i_2}$ ;
21 end
```

under criterion C_5 . By Algorithm 1, we set $i_1 = 2$, $i_2 = 4$, and $j_1 = 5$. Thus, we attempt to find Δ_{45}^2 by implementing Algorithm 1. Using the information generated in Example 1 and the parameters defined in Eq. (23), we obtain $a = 0.0144$, $b = 0.0144$, $c = 0.0111$, and $p = 0.0111$. Also, $\sqrt{\frac{p}{a} + \frac{b^2}{4a^2} - \frac{c}{a}} = 18.6882 > 0$, ensuring that Δ_{45}^2 is real. Setting $\epsilon = 0.1$, we have

$$\beta_1 = -\frac{b}{2a} + \sqrt{\frac{p}{a} + \frac{b^2}{4a^2} - \frac{c}{a}} + \epsilon = 0.4230 \text{ and}$$

$$\beta_2 = -\frac{b}{2a} - \sqrt{\frac{p}{a} + \frac{b^2}{4a^2} - \frac{c}{a}} + \epsilon = -8.4230$$

. Clearly, β_1 satisfies the feasibility condition but not β_2 . By increasing alternative A_4 's rating under criterion C_5 with $\Delta_{45}^2 = \beta_1$, we obtain the closeness coefficients of the alternatives as follows: $CC_1 = 0.6127$, $CC_2 = 0.3660$, $CC_3 = 0.5306$, and $CC_4 = 0.3705$. Note that only alternative A_4 's closeness coefficient has changed but the closeness coefficients of the other alternatives remain the same. Moreover, $CC_4 > CC_2$ now, i.e A_4 has the rank of alternative A_2 .

3.3. Finding reachable set of criteria

From the above analysis, it is clear that by changing alternative A_{i_2} 's rating under a criterion, the ranking of alternative A_{i_1} may be achievable or not. We are interested to identify all those criteria from C such that modifying any of these criteria will allow the decision maker to obtain the rank of alternative A_{i_1} . A straightforward way of identifying such criteria is the repeated application of Algorithm 1 for different values of the criteria index $j = 1, 2, \dots, n$. Let $\mathcal{C}_{i_1 i_2}$ be the set of criteria whereby changing any of them, A_{i_2} can achieve the rank of A_{i_1} . Obviously, $\mathcal{C}_{i_1 i_2} \subset C$ for any pair of alternatives (A_{i_1}, A_{i_2}) . When $\mathcal{C}_{i_1 i_2} = \emptyset$, it is not possible for alternative A_{i_2} to achieve the rank of A_{i_1} . In practice, $\mathcal{C}_{i_1 i_2}$ will allow the decision maker to identify a subset of the criteria set C from which one criterion can be chosen to improve its rating to obtain the rank of A_{i_1} .

Algorithm 2: Find $\mathcal{C}_{i_1 i_2}$

Input : Decision matrix D , weight vector w , i_2 , i_1
Output: $\mathcal{C}_{i_1 i_2}$

```

1  $\mathcal{C}_{i_1 i_2} = \emptyset$ 
2 for  $j = 1$  to  $n$  do
3   if  $sc_j^U \neq a_{i_1 j}$  then
4      $t = \text{find } \Delta_{i_1 j}^{i_1}$  by Algorithm 1;
5     if  $t = \text{Not possible to achieve the rank of } i_1 \text{ by } i_2$  then
6        $\mathcal{C}_{i_1 i_2} = \mathcal{C}_{i_1 i_2}$ ;
7       continue;
8     else
9        $\mathcal{C}_{i_1 i_2} = \mathcal{C}_{i_1 i_2} \cup \{j\}$ 
10    end
11  end
12 end

```

Example 3. We consider the data of the Example 1 and Example 2. In Example 2, we have found that by changing alternative A_4 's rating under C_5 , one can attain the rank of A_2 . We are interested to identify the other criteria whose modification in the rating will allow us to obtain the rank of A_2 . In fact, we will identify the set $\mathcal{C}_{i_1 i_2}$ by implementing **Algorithm 2**. According to **Algorithm 2**, we set $i_1 = 2$ and $i_2 = 4$. First, we check for $j_1 = 1$, i.e. the criterion C_1 . Since $sc_1^U \neq a_{41}$, we proceed to implement **Algorithm 1** to find Δ_{41}^2 . We obtain $\Delta_{41}^2 > 0.0530$, which satisfies our feasibility condition. Therefore, the rank of alternative A_2 is achievable by A_4 with an increment of more than 0.0530 over the current rating and therefore, $C_1 \in \mathcal{C}_{24}$. Repeating the check for the rest of the criteria, we obtain $\mathcal{C}_{24} = \{C_1, C_2, C_3, C_4, C_5, C_6\}$.

3.4. Finding reachable set of alternatives

Also of interest, is that by changing alternative A_{i_2} 's rating under criterion C_{j_1} , which of the other alternatives' ranks are achievable. Such a set of alternatives can also be easily obtained with the repeated application of **Algorithm 1** over the alternatives' index set I . Before illustrating the algorithm for finding such a set of alternatives, we will set the notation. Let $\mathcal{A}_{i_2 j_1}$ be the set of alternatives whose ranks are

achievable by changing A_{i_2} 's rating under the criterion C_{j_1} . One immediate property of $\mathcal{A}_{i_2j_1}$ is that $\mathcal{A}_{i_2j_1} = \emptyset$ if any of the following conditions hold:

- there is no alternative whose rank is achievable by changing the rating of the i_1 -th alternative's j -th criteria;
- the i_1 -th alternative is the best alternative;
- $a_{i_2j_1} = sc_j^U$.

By implementing **Algorithm 3**, we can find the set $\mathcal{A}_{i_2j_1}$ for any $i_2 \in I$ and $j \in J$. In the context of the strategic manipulation of the decision information, the set $\mathcal{A}_{i_2j_1}$ provides the overview of changing the rank of alternative A_{i_1} with a unilateral change in the criterion C_{j_1} .

Algorithm 3: Find $\mathcal{A}_{i_2j_1}$

Input : Decision matrix D , weight vector w , i_2 , j_1
Output: $\mathcal{A}_{i_1j_1}$

```

1  $\mathcal{A}_{i_2j_1} = \emptyset$ 
2 for  $i \in I \setminus \{i_2\}$  do
3    $t = \text{find } \Delta_{i_2j_1}^{i_1}$ ;
4   if  $t = \text{Not possible to achieve the rank of } i \text{ by } i_2$  then
5      $\mathcal{A}_{i_1j_1} = \mathcal{A}_{i_1j_1}$ ;
6     continue;
7   else
8      $\mathcal{A}_{i_2j_1} = \mathcal{A}_{i_2j_1} \cup \{i\}$ 
9   end
10 end

```

Example 4. Consider the data of Example 1 and the results of Example 2 and Example 3. In Example 2, we have found that by changing the C_5 criterion's rating, A_4 can obtain A_2 's rank. Now, we want to identify whether there are also other alternatives' ranks achievable by changing C_4 's rating. In short, we want to identify the set $\mathcal{A}_{i_2j_1}$ with the help of Algorithm 3. Here, $i_2 = 4$ and $j_1 = 5$. First, we check for A_1 and find that there are no real values of Δ_{45}^1 and $\Delta_{45}^{1'}$ which satisfies our feasibility condition. Therefore, A_1 's rank is not achievable. Next, we check for $i = 3$. As per the earlier case, no real values of Δ_{45}^3 and $\Delta_{45}^{3'}$ are obtained and so A_3 's rank is not achievable. Finally, we obtain $\mathcal{A}_{45} = \{2\}$.

3.5. Find the nature of closeness coefficient

In Proposition 1, we have established the fact that when the change $\Delta_{i_2j_1}$ remains in the range $\frac{L}{j_1} < a_{i_2j_1} \pm \Delta_{i_2j_1} < sc_{j_1}^U$, the relative closeness coefficients of the rest of the alternatives $A \setminus \{A_{i_2}\}$ hold the same values. Any change $\Delta_{i_2j_1}$ in the rating $a_{i_2j_1}$ will lead to a large variation in the resultant closeness coefficient of alternative A_{i_2} , CC_{i_2} . This naturally prompts us to investigate the nature of the closeness coefficient of A_{i_2} under a change in the j_1 -th criterion rating. For subsequent development, we set certain notations associated with the closeness coefficient. Since we are considering only a change in the input

decision information of the i_2 -th alternative's j_1 -th criterion rating $a_{i_2j_1}$ and the rest of the items remain unaltered, the distances from the positive and negative ideal solutions of alternative A_{i_2} can be viewed as a function of $a_{i_2j_1}$. For emphasis, we denote this by $D^+(a_{i_2j_1})$ and $D^-(a_{i_2j_1})$. It is clear that the closeness coefficient is also a function of $a_{i_2j_1}$ and we denote it by $CC_{i_2}(a_{i_2j_1})$. The nature of $CC_{i_2}(a_{i_2j_1})$ under a change in $a_{i_2j_1}$ shall be established in the following proposition.

Proposition 3. If $a_{i_2j_1} \neq sc_{j_1}^L$ or $a_{i_2j_1} \neq \min_i sc_{j_1}^U$, then the closeness coefficient $CC_{i_2}(a_{i_2j_1})$ is increasing w.r.t. $a_{i_2j_1}$ over the interval $sc_{j_1}^L \leq a_{i_2j_1} \leq sc_{j_1}^U$ and the rest of the alternatives' closeness coefficients remain the same.

Proof. According to Eq. (12), we have

$$CC_{i_2}(a_{i_2j_1}) = \frac{D^-(a_{i_2j_1})}{D^+(a_{i_2j_1}) + D^-(a_{i_2j_1})}. \quad (27)$$

From Eqs. (10) and (11), it is clear that $CC_{i_2}(a_{i_2j_1})$ is a differentiable function of $a_{i_2j_1}$ in the interval $sc_{j_1}^L \leq a_{i_2j_1} \leq sc_{j_1}^U$. Therefore, we differentiate both sides of Eq. (27) with respect to $a_{i_2j_1}$, obtaining

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dCC_{i_2}(a_{i_2j_1})}{a_{i_2j_1}} &= \frac{(D^+(a_{i_2j_1})+D^-(a_{i_2j_1}))(D^-(a_{i_2j_1}))^{-1}(a_{i_2j_1}-NI_{j_1})-D^-(a_{i_2j_1})((D^+(a_{i_2j_1}))^{-1}(a_{i_2j_1}-PI_{j_1}))+D^-(a_{i_2j_1}))^{-1}(a_{i_2j_1}-NI_{j_1}))}{(D^+(a_{i_2j_1})+D^-(a_{i_2j_1}))^2} \\ &= \frac{D^-(a_{i_2j_1})^{-1}D^+(a_{i_2j_1})(a_{i_2j_1}-NI_{j_1})-(D^+(a_{i_2j_1}))^{-1}D^-(a_{i_2j_1})(a_{i_2j_1}-PI_{j_1})}{(D^+(a_{i_2j_1})+D^-(a_{i_2j_1}))^2} \\ &= \frac{(D^+(a_{i_2j_1}))^2(a_{i_2j_1}-NI_{j_1})-(D^-(a_{i_2j_1}))^2(a_{i_2j_1}-PI_{j_1})}{D^+(a_{i_2j_1})D^-(a_{i_2j_1})(D^+(a_{i_2j_1})+D^-(a_{i_2j_1}))^2} \\ &= \frac{(D^+(a_{i_2j_1}))^2(a_{i_2j_1}-NI_{j_1})+(D^-(a_{i_2j_1}))^2(PI_{j_1}-a_{i_2j_1})}{D^+(a_{i_2j_1})D^-(a_{i_2j_1})(D^+(a_{i_2j_1})+D^-(a_{i_2j_1}))^2} \end{aligned}$$

From Eq. (28), it is clear that $\frac{dCC_{i_2}(a_{i_2j_1})}{a_{i_2j_1}} \geq 0$ for all $a_{i_2j_1} \in (\min_i a_{ij_1}, \max_i a_{ij_1})$. Hence, $CC_{i_2}(a_{i_2j_1})$ is increasing in the interval $[sc_{j_1}^L, sc_{j_1}^U]$. \square

Remark 3. From Proposition 3, it is clear that the index $i_2 \in I$ and $j_1 \in J$ are arbitrary choices. Therefore, it is valid for all pairs of values of i_2 and j_1 as long as they satisfy the condition of Proposition 3.

Remark 4. As $CC_{i_2}(a_{i_2j_1})$ is increasing over the interval $sc_{j_1}^L \leq a_{i_2j_1} \leq sc_{j_1}^U$, the maximum and minimum values of $CC_{i_2}(a_{i_2j_1})$ are obtained at the end points of the interval, i.e. at $sc_{j_1}^L$ and $sc_{j_1}^U$, respectively.

Example 5. Consider the data of the decision problem described in Example 1. We note that the maximum and minimum values of the rating of criteria C_6 are 5 and 9 respectively. If we increase the ratings of $a_{46} \in [5, 9]$, the closeness coefficient of the alternative, CC_4 , will increase as shown in Fig. 1.

Figure 1: Changes in closeness coefficient of alternative A_4 with a change in a_{46}

3.6. Find upper and lower rank achievable alternatives

From Remark 4, we can determine the minimum and maximum achievable values of the closeness coefficient $CC_{i_2}(a_{i_2j_1})$ under a change in the j_1 -th criterion without affecting the other alternatives' closeness coefficients. Let $CC_{i_2}^{max}(a_{i_2j_1})$ and $CC_{i_2}^{min}(a_{i_2j_1})$ be the maximum and minimum values of $CC_{i_2}(a_{i_2j_1})$ in the interval $sc_{j_1}^L \leq a_{i_2j_1} \leq sc_{j_1}^U$ respectively. We can identify the set $\mathcal{A}_{i_2j_1}$ with the help of $CC_{i_2}(a_{i_2j_1})^{max}$ and $CC_{i_2}^{min}(a_{i_2j_1})$. To identify whether an alternative belongs to the set $\mathcal{A}_{i_2j_1}$ or not, we just need to compare the alternative's closeness coefficient with $CC_{i_2}^{max}(a_{i_2j_1})$. Therefore, this approach of identifying the set $\mathcal{A}_{i_2j_1}$ requires less effort than **Algorithm 3**. Let $I_{i_2}^>$ be the set of all those alternatives, whose rank order is better than the rank of A_{i_2} i.e. $I_{i_2}^> = \{i \in I | CC_i > CC_{i_2}\}$. To find the set of the higher ranked alternatives $\mathcal{A}_{i_2j_1}^>$, whose rank is achievable by changing the j_1 -th criterion rating of the i_2 -th alternative, we provide **Algorithm 4** as shown below:

Algorithm 4: Find $\mathcal{A}_{i_2j_1}^>$

Input : decision matrix D , weight vector w , i_2 , j_1 and $C_{i_2}^{max}(a_{i_2j_1})$

Output: $\mathcal{A}_{i_2j_1}$

```

1  $\mathcal{A}_{i_2j_1}^> = \emptyset$ 
2 for  $i \in I_{i_2}^>$  do
3   if  $C_{i_2}^{max}(a_{i_2j_1}) > C_i$  then
4      $\mathcal{A}_{i_2j_1}^> = \mathcal{A}_{i_2j_1}^> \cup \{i\}$ 
5   else
6     continue;
7   end
8 end

```

Example 6. Consider the decision making problem discussed in Example 1. We reinvestigate the problem of identifying the set $\mathcal{A}_{45}^>$ i.e. find those higher ranked alternatives, whose ranks are attainable by A_4 by changing the rating under C_5 . We implement **Algorithm 4**. The minimum and maximum ratings of C_5 are

$sc_5^L = \min_i a_{i5} = 3$ and $sc_5^U = \max_i a_{i5} = 7$ respectively. We can vary the rating of A_4 under criterion C_5 in the range $a_{45} \in [3, 7]$. According to Proposition 3, we find the maximum value of the closeness coefficient at the right end point 7 of the interval and the value is $CC_4^{max}(a_{45} = 7) = 0.4383$. From Example 1, $I_4^> = \{1, 2, 3\}$. We feed this information into **Algorithm 4** to yield $\mathcal{A}_{45}^> = \{2\}$ as $CC_4^{max}(a_{45})$ only exceeds CC_2 .

After receiving the initial recommendation from TOPSIS, a decision maker may wish to know whether the deterioration of an alternative's rating under a criterion may lead to a lower rank position from the current rank. The possibility of achieving such targets of downgrading an alternative's rank under a criterion can be found by using the minimum value of the closeness coefficient $CC_{i_2}^{min}(a_{i_2 j_1})$. Let $\mathcal{A}_{i_2 j_1}^<$ be the set of alternatives, whose ranks are achievable by downgrading the current rating of alternative A_{i_2} under the j_1 -th criterion. We further assume that $I_{i_2 j_1}^<$ is the set of alternatives, whose ranks are lower than the i_2 -th alternative's rank. We can identify $\mathcal{A}_{i_2 j_1}^<$ with the help of the following algorithm:

Algorithm 5: Find $\mathcal{A}_{i_2 j_1}^<$

Input : decision matrix D , weight vector w , i_2 , j_1 and $CC_{i_2}^{min}(a_{i_2 j_1})$

Output: $\mathcal{A}_{i_2 j_1}^<$

```

1  $\mathcal{A}_{i_2 j_1}^< = \emptyset$ 
2 for  $i \in I_{i_2}^>$  do
3   if  $CC_{i_2}^{min}(a_{i_2 j_1}) < CC_i$  then
4      $\mathcal{A}_{i_2 j_1}^< = \mathcal{A}_{i_2 j_1}^< \cup \{i\}$ 
5   else
6     continue;
7   end
8 end

```

Example 7. Consider the data of Example 1. We are interested to identify the alternatives whose ranks are achievable by downgrading the rating of alternative A_3 under the criterion C_5 with the help of **Algorithm 5**. The minimum and maximum ratings of C_6 are $sc_5^L = \min_i a_{i5} = 3$ and $sc_5^U = \max_i a_{i5} = 7$ respectively. One can vary the rating a_{15} in the range $[5, 9]$. With the help of Proposition 3, we obtain the minimum value of the closeness coefficient as $CC_1^{min}(a_{16}) = 0.5378$. Further, we have $I_3^< = \{2, 4\}$. With this input information, we implement **Algorithm 5** to obtain $\mathcal{A}_{35} = \emptyset$.

4. Rank reversing

Often times, a decision maker may wonder how the ranking order of a pair of alternatives in the initial recommendation could reverse without affecting the other alternatives' ranking order. Such targets of reversing the ranking order of the alternatives could be achieved by changing the alternatives' rating under different criteria. Here, we provide a systematic way of rank reversing a particular pair of alternatives. Let (A_{i_1}, A_{i_2}) be the pair of alternatives and their current ranking indices are given by $r(A_{i_1}) = r_1$ and $r(A_{i_2}) = r_2$. Our

problem is how to reverse the alternatives' ranking indices i.e. $r^{new}(A_{i_1}) = r_2$ and $r^{new}(A_{i_2}) = r_1$. Finding the solution to this problem requires two stages. In the first stage, we need to check whether it is feasible or not. If the answer regarding feasibility in the first stage is affirmative, then we proceed to the second stage. In the second stage, we determine the amount of change in the rating of the alternatives required for reversing the phenomenon. Suppose the rank order of the alternatives is $r_1 > r_2$. That means we need to downgrade A_{i_1} 's rating and upgrade A_{i_2} 's rating to reverse the rank order.

There are two ways to find out whether rank reversing is possible or not. One way is to find the set of all the criteria by interchanging the A_{i_1} (A_{i_2}) which can achieve the rank of A_{i_2} (A_{i_1}), i.e. finding the reachable set of criteria $\mathcal{C}_{i_1 i_2}$ ($\mathcal{C}_{i_2 i_1}$). When $\mathcal{C}_{i_1 i_2} \neq \emptyset$ and $\mathcal{C}_{i_2 i_1} \neq \emptyset$, the rank of the pair (A_{i_1}, A_{i_2}) is reversible. Now, one can reverse the ranking order of the alternatives by changing A_{i_1} 's rating under any of the criteria in $\mathcal{C}_{i_1 i_2}$ and A_{i_2} 's ratings under any of the criterion in $\mathcal{C}_{i_2 i_1}$. Therefore, one can reverse the rank order of the alternatives in $|\mathcal{C}_{i_1 i_2}| \times |\mathcal{C}_{i_2 i_1}|$ ways (where $|C|$ denotes the cardinality of the set C). In each case, the required change can be computed by utilizing **Algorithm 1**.

Another way is to find the upper and lower rank achievable sets. For alternative A_{i_1} , we find the lower rank achievable set $\mathcal{A}_{i_1 j}^<$, $j \in J$. For A_{i_2} , we find the upper rank achievable set $\mathcal{A}_{i_2 j}^>$, $j \in J$. If $A_{i_2} \in \cup_{j \in J} \mathcal{A}_{i_1 j}^<$ and $A_{i_1} \in \cup_{j \in J} \mathcal{A}_{i_2 j}^>$, then the ranks of the alternatives (A_{i_1}, A_{i_2}) are reversible. Otherwise it is not reversible. The identification of the criteria whose change is required to achieve the rank of A_{i_2} using A_{i_1} is also possible from the set $\mathcal{A}_{i_1 j}^<$, $j \in J$. In fact, there is a relationship between $\mathcal{C}_{i_1 i_2}$ and $\mathcal{A}_{i_1 j}^<$, $j \in J$ that can be expressed as $\mathcal{C}_{i_1 i_2} = \{C_j | A_{i_2} \in \mathcal{A}_{i_1 j}^<, j \in J\}$. Similarly, the set $\mathcal{C}_{i_2 i_1}$ is related to the lower rank achievable sets under different criteria as follows: $\mathcal{C}_{i_2 i_1} = \{C_j | A_{i_1} \in \mathcal{A}_{i_2 j}^>, j \in J\}$. In the second stage, we follow the same procedure for finding the change under different criteria.

5. Rank sensitive interval (RSI)

The stability of the ranking order of the alternatives affects the quality of the TOPSIS based decision making model. Addressing this issue allows us to exhibit the robustness of the current alternatives' ranking order. In this section, we discuss the stability of the TOPSIS generated ranking order of the alternatives.

The changes in an alternative's rating under a criterion may alter the current ranking order of the alternatives. Sometimes, a perturbation may affect the ranking order while some isolated cases a substantial change is not material to the ranking order. Therefore, a systematic analysis is required to determine the behaviour of the ranking order of the alternatives under a change in decision information. We first introduce the notion of *rank sensitivity interval* to show how the rating of an alternative under a criterion can be modified without altering the current ranking order of the alternatives.

We recall that $r(A_i)$ denotes the rank position of alternative A_i . Suppose $r(A_{\sigma(1)}) < r(A_{\sigma(2)}) < \dots < r(A_{\sigma(m)})$ is the ranking order of the alternatives, and $(\sigma(1), \sigma(2), \dots, \sigma(m))$ is a permutation on $(1, 2, \dots, m)$. $r(A_{\sigma(i)}) < r(A_{\sigma(i+1)})$ means that $A_{\sigma(i)}$ has a better rank than $A_{\sigma(i+1)}$. Consider any three consecutive ranking alternatives, $r(A_{\sigma(i-1)}) < r(A_{\sigma(i)}) < r(A_{\sigma(i+1)})$, where $i \in \{2, 3, \dots, m-1\}$. Clearly, if we preserve

Algorithm 6: Find rank sensitive interval $RSI_{ij} = [a_{ij}^L, a_{ij}^U]$

Input : decision matrix D , weight vector w , i, j
Output: rank sensitive interval $RSI_{ij} = [a_{ij}^L, a_{ij}^U]$

- 1 Find CC by implementing **TOPSIS**
- 2 $k =$ rank position of A_i
- 3 **if** $a_{ij} = sc_j^U$ **then**
- 4 | $[a_{ij}^L, a_{ij}^U] = [a_{ij} a_{ij}]$;
- 5 **else if** $a_{ij} = sc_j^L$ **then**
- 6 | $[a_{ij}^L, a_{ij}^U] = [a_{ij} a_{ij}]$;
- 7 **else**
- 8 | **if** $k = 1$ **then**
- 9 | | find $(k + 1)$ -th rank position of alternative $A_{\sigma(k+1)}$
- 10 | | $t =$ find $\Delta_{\sigma(k)j}^{\sigma(k+1)}$ implementing **Algorithm 1**
- 11 | | **if** *Not possible to achieve the rank of $A_{\sigma(k+1)}$ by $A_{\sigma(k)}$* **then**
- 12 | | | $[a_{ij}^L, a_{ij}^U] = [sc_j^L, a_{ij}]$
- 13 | | **else**
- 14 | | | $[a_{ij}^L, a_{ij}^U] = [a_{ij} - t + \epsilon, a_{ij}]$
- 15 | | **end**
- 16 | **else if** $k = m$ **then**
- 17 | | find $(k - 1)$ -th rank position of alternative $A_{\sigma(k-1)}$
- 18 | | $t_1 =$ find $\Delta_{\sigma(k)j}^{\sigma(k-1)}$ implementing **Algorithm 1**
- 19 | | **if** *Not possible to achieve the rank of $A_{\sigma(k-1)}$ by $A_{\sigma(k)}$* **then**
- 20 | | | $[a_{ij}^L, a_{ij}^U] = [sc_j^L, sc_j^U]$
- 21 | | **else**
- 22 | | | $[a_{ij}^L, a_{ij}^U] = [sc_j^L, a_{ij} + t_1 - \epsilon]$
- 23 | | **end**
- 24 | **else**
- 25 | | find $(k - 1)$ -th and $(k + 1)$ -th rank position of alternatives: $A_{\sigma(k-1)} A_{\sigma(k+1)}$
- 26 | | $t_2 =$ find $\Delta_{\sigma(k)j}^{\sigma(k-1)}$ implementing **Algorithm 1**
- 27 | | **if** $t_2 =$ *Not possible to achieve the rank of $A_{\sigma(k-1)}$ by $A_{\sigma(k)}$* **then**
- 28 | | | $a_{ij}^U = sc_j^U$
- 29 | | **else**
- 30 | | | $a_{ij}^U = a_{ij} + t_2 - \epsilon$
- 31 | | **end**
- 32 | | $t_3 =$ find $\Delta_{\sigma(k)j}^{\sigma(k+1)}$ implementing **Algorithm 1**
- 33 | | **if** $t_3 =$ *Not possible to achieve the rank of $A_{\sigma(k+1)}$ by $A_{\sigma(k)}$* **then**
- 34 | | | $a_{ij}^L = sc_j^U$
- 35 | | **else**
- 36 | | | $a_{ij}^L = a_{ij} - t_3 + \epsilon$
- 37 | | **end**
- 38 | **end**
- 39 **end**

the ranking order of these consecutive alternatives under a change in the rating of alternative $A_{\sigma(i)}$ against criterion C_j , then the other alternatives' ranking positions will remain the same. The closeness coefficients of the corresponding alternatives obey the relation $CC_{\sigma(i-1)} > CC_{\sigma(i)} > CC_{\sigma(i+1)}$. Finding the rank sensitive interval (RSI) of alternative $A_{\sigma(i)}$ under criterion C_j ($j \in J$) means that there exists an interval $RSI_{\sigma(i)j}$

in which alternative $A_{\sigma(i)}$'s rating under criterion C_j , $a_{\sigma(i)j}$, can vary without affecting the current ranking order of the alternatives $r(A_{\sigma(i-1)}) < r(A_{\sigma(i)}) < r(A_{\sigma(i+1)})$. Let $RSI_{\sigma(i)j} = [a_{\sigma(i)j}^L, a_{\sigma(i)j}^U]$, where $a_{\sigma(i)j}^L$ and $a_{\sigma(i)j}^U$ are the lower and upper bounds of $a_{\sigma(i)j}$ respectively.

When $a_{\sigma(i)j} = sc_j^U$ or $a_{\sigma(i)j} = sc_j^L$, we set $RSI_{\sigma(i)j} = [a_{\sigma(i)j}^L, a_{\sigma(i)j}^U] = [a_{\sigma(i)j}, a_{\sigma(i)j}]$. In this case, a change in $a_{\sigma(i)j}$ may lead to changes in the overall ranking order of the alternatives (as explained in Proposition 1).

To preserve the current ranking order of the alternatives, we keep it as it is.

When $a_{\sigma(i)j} \neq sc_j^U$ or $a_{\sigma(i)j} \neq sc_j^L$, two situations arise for finding the upper and lower bounds:

- Upper bound ($a_{\sigma(i)j}^U$): since $r(A_{\sigma(i-1)}) < r(A_{\sigma(i)})$, the rank position of $A_{\sigma(i-1)}$ is better than that of $A_{\sigma(i)}$, that is, $CC_{\sigma(i-1)} > CC_{\sigma(i)}$. Finding the upper bound is determined by whether the rank of $A_{\sigma(i-1)}$ is achievable by changing alternative $A_{\sigma(i)}$'s rating under C_j or not. If it is achievable, then $a_{\sigma(i)j}^U = a_{\sigma(i)j} + \Delta_{\sigma(i)j}^{\sigma(i-1)} - \epsilon$, where $\Delta_{\sigma(i)j}^{\sigma(i-1)}$ is obtained by utilizing **Algorithm 1**. Otherwise, $a_{\sigma(i)j}^U = sc_j^U$.
- Lower bound ($a_{\sigma(i)j}^L$): since $r(A_{\sigma(i)}) < r(A_{\sigma(i+1)})$, the rank position of $A_{\sigma(i)}$ is better than that of $A_{\sigma(i+1)}$, that is, $CC_{\sigma(i)} > CC_{\sigma(i+1)}$. Similarly, finding the lower bound is determined by whether the rank of $A_{\sigma(i+1)}$ is achievable by changing alternative $A_{\sigma(i)}$'s rating under C_j or not. If it is achievable, then $a_{\sigma(i)j}^L = a_{\sigma(i)j} - \Delta_{\sigma(i)j}^{\sigma(i+1)} + \epsilon$, where $\Delta_{\sigma(i)j}^{\sigma(i+1)}$ is obtained by utilizing **Algorithm 1**. Otherwise, $a_{\sigma(i)j}^L = sc_j^L$.
- When $i = 1$, we will consider the ranking position of the first two alternatives, $r(A_{\sigma(1)}) < r(A_{\sigma(2)})$, to compute the rank sensitive interval of alternative $A_{\sigma(1)}$ as it will preserve the ranking position of the rest of the alternatives. The lower bound of the rank sensitive interval can be found by checking the condition whether the rank of $A_{\sigma(2)}$ is achievable by changing alternative $A_{\sigma(1)}$'s rating under C_j or not. If it is achievable, then $a_{\sigma(1)j}^L = a_{\sigma(1)j} - \Delta_{\sigma(1)j}^{\sigma(2)} + \epsilon$, where $\Delta_{\sigma(1)j}^{\sigma(2)}$ is obtained by utilizing **Algorithm 1**. If not, then $a_{\sigma(1)j}^L = sc_j^L$. In this case, the upper bound will be $a_{\sigma(1)j}^U = sc_j^U$.
- When $k = m$, it suffices to consider the ranking position of the last two alternatives $r(A_{\sigma(m-1)}) < r(A_{\sigma(m)})$ to find the rank sensitive interval of alternative $A_{\sigma(m)}$ under different criteria. The upper bound of the rank sensitive interval can be computed by checking the condition whether the rank of $A_{\sigma(m-1)}$ is achievable by changing alternative $A_{\sigma(m)}$'s rating under C_j or not. If it is achievable, then $a_{\sigma(m)j}^U = a_{\sigma(m)j} + \Delta_{\sigma(m)j}^{\sigma(m-1)} - \epsilon$, where $\Delta_{\sigma(m)j}^{\sigma(m-1)}$ is obtained by utilizing **Algorithm 1**. If not, then $a_{\sigma(m)j}^U = sc_j^U$. In this case, the lower bound will be $a_{\sigma(m)j}^L = sc_j^L$.

The computational procedure for the rank sensitive interval is summarized in **Algorithm 6**.

Table I: Ratings of 25 universities and their rankings based on closeness coefficient

x_i	C_1	C_2	C_3	C_4	C_5	Closeness Coefficient (CC_i)
x_1	86.7	99.5	99.1	63.7	95	0.8940(3)
x_2	87.8	97.8	97.5	51.5	93	0.8800(5)
x_3	90.3	97.5	99.5	92.6	59.7	0.9003(2)
x_4	89.1	96.7	99.9	60.5	77.6	0.8885(4)
x_5	87.3	91.9	100	88.4	87.6	0.9026(1)
x_6	84.2	98.4	99.7	46.4	79.7	0.8569(8)
x_7	85.7	93.9	99.6	58	78.7	0.8694(6)
x_8	81.7	88.7	96.7	71.6	96.6	0.8578(7)
x_9	85.3	90.1	99.4	39.8	69.6	0.8334(10)
x_{10}	76.4	92	94.3	60.3	98.1	0.8314(12)
x_{11}	83.7	90.1	98.5	56.9	61.3	0.8396(9)
x_{12}	86.7	87	98.4	45.1	64.6	0.8318(11)
x_{13}	76.1	88.1	98.4	95.8	70.6	0.8303(13)
x_{14}	82.2	83.3	98.8	41.3	76.6	0.8099(17)
x_{15}	80.7	88.1	97.9	48.6	59.5	0.8148(15)
x_{16}	74.4	88.2	94.6	41.2	94.6	0.7972(18)
x_{17}	80.7	80.6	98.3	100	62.5	0.8202(14)
x_{18}	77.4	84.5	99.8	37.5	64.5	0.7874(22)
x_{19}	76.2	86.6	97.6	34.6	69.2	0.7873(23)
x_{20}	72.6	86.7	96.9	78.2	59.2	0.7970(19)
x_{21}	77.2	86.3	95.7	46.2	55.8	0.7914(20)
x_{22}	77.4	88.2	81.3	61.9	95.8	0.8123(16)
x_{23}	74.6	84.8	92.6	46.5	80.1	0.7884(21)
x_{24}	65.8	83.7	99.7	50.4	79.1	0.7552(24)
x_{25}	71.8	72	94.9	33.7	92.2	0.7311(25)

Data source: www.timeshighereducation.com, accessed: 25/09/2017

6. Experimental Analysis

Consider the 25 universities from the Times Higher Education¹ world universities ranking as a set of alternatives, denoted by $\{x_1, x_2, \dots, x_{25}\}$. These alternatives are ranked based on the following criteria:

- C_1 : Teaching (learning environment)
- C_2 : Research (volume income and reputation)
- C_3 : Citations (research influence)
- C_4 : Industry income (knowledge transfer)
- C_5 : International outlook (staff, students, and research)

The relative importance of the criteria is set as $w = (0.3, 0.3, 0.2, 0.1, 0.1)$ and all the criteria belong to the benefit criteria category. The cardinal scale $[0, 100]$ is used to rate the alternatives against the criteria and the ratings of the universities against the criteria are given in Table I. Before the normalization step can take place, we add the fictitious alternatives with ratings under the criteria as follows: $F_1 = (100, 100, 100, 100, 100)$ and $F_2 = (0, 0, 0, 0, 0)$. We apply the Linear Scale Transformation (Max-Min),

¹www.timeshighereducation.com

described in Eq.(3), to normalize the rating of the alternatives. Executing Steps 2-6, we compute the closeness coefficients of alternatives $\{x_1, x_2, \dots, x_{25}\}$ and the results are listed in Table I. x_5 is the best alternative while x_{25} is the worst.

Table II: Rank sensitive interval

x_i	$[RSI_i(a_{i1})^L, RSI_i(a_{i1})^U]$	$[RSI_i(a_{i2})^L, RSI_i(a_{i2})^U]$	$[RSI_i(a_{i3})^L, RSI_i(a_{i3})^U]$	$[RSI_i(a_{i4})^L, RSI_i(a_{i4})^U]$	$[RSI_i(a_{i5})^L, RSI_i(a_{i5})^U]$
x_1	[85.426, 88.2372]	[94.966, 100]	[91.8356, 100]	[59.2594, 69.1751]	[81.6025, 100]
x_2	[84.9072, 90.4549]	[91.6955, 100]	[87.1157, 100]	[43.8934, 57.8508]	[72.0188, 100]
x_3	[88.5215, 90.9889]	[93.8003, 100]	[91.4324, 100]	[79.919, 100]	[55.3206, 61.3058]
x_4	[86.7207, 90.7889]	[92.2236, 100]	[89.4969, 100]	[53.8065, 65.0132]	[67.4101, 86.6399]
x_5	[86.8138, 100]	[91.1888, 100]	[100, 100]	[84.2399, 100]	[83.6278, 100]
x_6	[79.6779, 84.4389]	[88.7331, 99.5478]	[82.3089, 100]	[32.5713, 47.1099]	[55.2216, 81.4905]
x_7	[82.7524, 88.671]	[89.0667, 100]	[86.7914, 100]	[48.0876, 68.1297]	[63.2158, 100]
x_8	[81.5092, 84.3557]	[88.4164, 93.21]	[95.3642, 100]	[70.4528, 97.692]	[92.2687, 100]
x_9	[84.7916, 87.4343]	[89.4261, 93.1581]	[96.04, 100]	[38.4498, 45.2628]	[67.1493, 81.4377]
x_{10}	[76.1505, 76.4782]	[91.4454, 92.1788]	[92.8384, 94.8046]	[58.8905, 60.7481]	[91.5004, 100]
x_{11}	[81.9749, 89.1358]	[87.6904, 100]	[90.1054, 100]	[50.3479, 80.4301]	[54.1679, 91.9911]
x_{12}	[86.5744, 87.2563]	[86.8723, 87.5664]	[97.606, 100]	[44.7638, 46.5755]	[64.1003, 66.8387]
x_{13}	[73.9591, 76.3458]	[84.6578, 88.532]	[86.7901, 100]	[69.8016, 100]	[56.6379, 72.497]
x_{14}	[78.5577, 82.9521]	[79.5111, 84.0905]	[84.5365, 100]	[29.1646, 43.7741]	[55.3514, 82.5957]
x_{15}	[80.0289, 82.2385]	[87.1581, 90.3958]	[93.9667, 100]	[45.9834, 54.7158]	[56.3018, 67.3441]
x_{16}	[74.3408, 77.5357]	[88.0973, 94.7149]	[94.2527, 100]	[40.9361, 55.9155]	[93.2633, 100]
x_{17}	[79.2946, 83.4814]	[79.2, 83.3681]	[90.8865, 100]	[100, 100]	[55.564, 79.1151]
x_{18}	[77.3641, 77.6718]	[84.4532, 84.8559]	[99.4998, 100]	[37.3598, 38.5607]	[64.2729, 66.2449]
x_{19}	[67.9856, 76.2346]	[75.9155, 86.6517]	[70.9287, 97.8438]	[3.0548, 34.7351]	[24.152, 69.4567]
x_{20}	[71.3502, 72.6549]	[84.6636, 86.7934]	[89.8228, 97.3327]	[66.7842, 78.7969]	[51.5366, 59.5568]
x_{21}	[76.3806, 78.726]	[85.1484, 88.5671]	[91.6471, 100]	[42.5948, 53.1498]	[51.5754, 64.2864]
x_{22}	[76.8182, 77.9769]	[87.2763, 89.1549]	[79.8122, 82.8415]	[58.6, 65.3467]	[85.7946, 100]
x_{23}	[74.3625, 75.3558]	[84.4588, 85.9106]	[91.4728, 96.955]	[45.3478, 50.2397]	[77.6386, 89.9487]
x_{24}	[60.2294, 73.3431]	[75.5599, 100]	[75.9788, 100]	[18, 100]	[34.3247, 100]
x_{25}	[0, 78.9807]	[0, 79.2248]	[0, 100]	[0, 74.4277]	[0, 100]

Next, we check the sensitivity of the current ranking order under a change of decision information and implement **Algorithm 6** to find the rank sensitive interval for each alternative against each criterion. The results are listed in Table II. The first entry of Table II, i.e., $[RSI_i(a_{11})^L, RSI_i(a_{11})^U] = [85.426, 88.2372]$ shows that if we vary the rating of alternative A_1 under criteria C_1 in the interval $[85.426, 88.2372]$, the current ranking positions of the alternatives remain unaltered. Further, Table III provides the decision maker with an overview of the robustness of the current ranking order of the alternatives, and depicts how the current ranking positions are unaffected by the perturbations in an alternative's ratings under a criterion. We have set $\epsilon = 0.0001$ in computing the rank sensitive interval, so as to allow us to differentiate the alternatives' closeness coefficients at the boundary points.

Given the initial recommendation from TOPSIS and the rank sensitivity interval results, a decision maker may wish to analyze a spectrum of scenarios related to the improvement or degradation of the ranking order of the target alternatives under a change in decision information. To achieve such targets, the decision maker needs an overview of how to change an alternative's ranking by changing its rating under a criterion. For this, we analyze the following scenarios to show the effect of a change from each criterion:

- how a change in the rating of a criterion affects the closeness coefficient of that alternative? By Proposition 1, we can identify the range of a particular attribute in which the changes in that criteria

Table III: Maximum and minimum values of closeness coefficients

x_i	$[CC_i^{min}(a_{i1}), CC_i^{max}(a_{i1})]$	$[CC_i^{min}(a_{i2}), CC_i^{max}(a_{i2})]$	$[CC_i^{min}(a_{i3}), CC_i^{max}(a_{i3})]$	$[CC_i^{min}(a_{i4}), CC_i^{max}(a_{i4})]$	$[CC_i^{min}(a_{i5}), CC_i^{max}(a_{i5})]$
x_1	[0.5545, 0.9291]	[0.5319, 0.8942]	[0.6654, 0.8942]	[0.8077, 0.9201]	[0.7974, 0.8946]
x_2	[0.5475, 0.9052]	[0.5294, 0.8816]	[0.6612, 0.8808]	[0.8077, 0.9235]	[0.7906, 0.881]
x_3	[0.5502, 0.9196]	[0.5377, 0.9022]	[0.6672, 0.9004]	[0.8007, 0.9016]	[0.813, 0.9377]
x_4	[0.5464, 0.9105]	[0.5327, 0.8914]	[0.6616, 0.8886]	[0.806, 0.9184]	[0.7982, 0.8975]
x_5	[0.5461, 0.9407]	[0.5377, 0.9173]	[0.6604, 0.9026]	[0.7988, 0.9056]	[0.799, 0.906]
x_6	[0.5464, 0.8919]	[0.5199, 0.858]	[0.6517, 0.857]	[0.7976, 0.8978]	[0.7811, 0.8626]
x_7	[0.541, 0.9025]	[0.5255, 0.8767]	[0.6514, 0.8695]	[0.7956, 0.8974]	[0.7862, 0.8765]
x_8	[0.5359, 0.9114]	[0.522, 0.8783]	[0.6425, 0.8592]	[0.7795, 0.8696]	[0.7727, 0.8581]
x_9	[0.5276, 0.8612]	[0.518, 0.8478]	[0.6363, 0.8336]	[0.7848, 0.8776]	[0.7677, 0.8443]
x_{10}	[0.5379, 0.9065]	[0.5059, 0.8422]	[0.6344, 0.8344]	[0.7688, 0.8501]	[0.757, 0.8316]
x_{11}	[0.529, 0.8752]	[0.516, 0.8546]	[0.6366, 0.8401]	[0.7766, 0.8627]	[0.7743, 0.8582]
x_{12}	[0.5207, 0.8554]	[0.5201, 0.8545]	[0.6338, 0.8324]	[0.779, 0.8678]	[0.7678, 0.8465]
x_{13}	[0.5358, 0.9083]	[0.5112, 0.8504]	[0.6292, 0.8309]	[0.7558, 0.8308]	[0.7627, 0.8409]
x_{14}	[0.5153, 0.8469]	[0.513, 0.843]	[0.6195, 0.8104]	[0.7647, 0.8459]	[0.747, 0.8163]
x_{15}	[0.5221, 0.8582]	[0.5065, 0.8339]	[0.6237, 0.8156]	[0.7638, 0.8427]	[0.7578, 0.8322]
x_{16}	[0.5256, 0.867]	[0.4959, 0.8158]	[0.6162, 0.8001]	[0.7552, 0.8303]	[0.7337, 0.798]
x_{17}	[0.5197, 0.8661]	[0.5199, 0.8666]	[0.6226, 0.8208]	[0.7478, 0.8202]	[0.7588, 0.8361]
x_{18}	[0.5149, 0.8392]	[0.4994, 0.8149]	[0.6069, 0.7875]	[0.75, 0.8225]	[0.7353, 0.7994]
x_{19}	[0.5177, 0.8442]	[0.4949, 0.8093]	[0.6088, 0.7884]	[0.752, 0.8258]	[0.7334, 0.7967]
x_{20}	[0.5253, 0.8805]	[0.4944, 0.8197]	[0.6111, 0.7985]	[0.7362, 0.8026]	[0.7437, 0.8136]
x_{21}	[0.515, 0.8458]	[0.4948, 0.8147]	[0.6106, 0.7937]	[0.747, 0.8184]	[0.7417, 0.8099]
x_{22}	[0.5189, 0.8743]	[0.4946, 0.8321]	[0.6298, 0.831]	[0.7525, 0.8285]	[0.7417, 0.8129]
x_{23}	[0.5148, 0.8564]	[0.4918, 0.8162]	[0.6083, 0.7929]	[0.7435, 0.8152]	[0.7287, 0.7932]
x_{24}	[0.5198, 0.8606]	[0.4791, 0.7843]	[0.5849, 0.7554]	[0.7157, 0.7748]	[0.7046, 0.7601]
x_{25}	[0.488, 0.7985]	[0.4875, 0.7976]	[0.5695, 0.7344]	[0.7038, 0.7621]	[0.6805, 0.7324]

does not affect the closeness coefficient of the other alternatives. After identifying the range for each criterion, we compute the maximum and minimum values of the closeness coefficient in that range by utilizing Remark 4. The results are summarized in Table III. For example, the first entry of Table III is obtained by changing the rating of x_1 under criterion C_1 (a_{11}) in the range $0 \leq a_{11} \pm \Delta_{11} \leq 100$ when the rest of the ratings remain unaltered and finding the maximum and minimum values of closeness coefficient in that range, i.e. [0.5545, 0.9291]. Note the minimum and maximum values of the closeness coefficient differ from the current value of 0.8940. Through Table II, the decision maker obtains an overview of the maximum and minimum achievable limits of the closeness coefficients of the alternatives under a criterion without affecting the other alternatives' closeness coefficients. Therefore, through this approach, a decision maker can better understand how by changing an alternative's current rating under a criterion, the alternative can obtain other possible ranking positions.

- which alternatives' rank are achievable by downgrading the current rating of an alternative under a specific criterion based on the restricted condition described in Proposition 1? To identify those alternatives under a change of each criterion, we apply the information regarding the minimum value of the closeness coefficient achievable under each criterion from Table III and implement the **Algorithm 5**. The results are listed in Table IV. For example, the first entry in Table IV $\mathcal{A}_{11}^<$ represents the set of alternatives whose ranks are achievable by downgrading the current rating of x_1 under criterion C_1 , i.e. $\{x_2, x_4, x_6 - x_{25}\}$. So, the alternative x_1 can achieve the ranks of the alternatives $\{x_2, x_4, x_6 - x_{25}\}$ and no alternative reaches the position of x_5 for $\mathcal{A}_{11}^<$. As x_{25} is the worst ranked alternative, there is

Table IV: Achievable lower rank alternatives with a change in attributes

x_i	rank	$\mathcal{A}_{i1}^<$	$\mathcal{A}_{i2}^<$	$\mathcal{A}_{i3}^<$	$\mathcal{A}_{i4}^<$	$\mathcal{A}_{i5}^<$
x_1	3	$\{x_2, x_4, x_6 - x_{25}\}$	$\{x_2, x_4, x_6 - x_{25}\}$	$\{x_2, x_4, x_6 - x_{25}\}$	$\{x_2, x_4, x_6 - x_{15}, x_{17}, x_{22}\}$	$\{x_2, x_4, x_6 - x_{15}, x_{17}, x_{22}\}$
x_2	5	$\{x_6 - x_{25}\}$	$\{x_6 - x_{25}\}$	$\{x_6 - x_{25}\}$	$\{x_6 - x_{15}, x_{17}, x_{22}\}$	$\{x_6 - x_{17}, x_{20} - x_{22}\}$
x_3	2	$\{x_1, x_2, x_4, x_6 - x_{25}\}$	$\{x_1, x_2, x_4, x_6 - x_{25}\}$	$\{x_1, x_2, x_4, x_6 - x_{25}\}$	$\{x_1, x_2, x_4, x_6 - x_{15}, x_{17}, x_{22}\}$	$\{x_1, x_2, x_4, x_6 - x_{13}, x_{15}, x_{17}\}$
x_4	4	$\{x_2, x_6 - x_{25}\}$	$\{x_2, x_6 - x_{25}\}$	$\{x_2, x_6 - x_{25}\}$	$\{x_2, x_6 - x_{15}, x_{17}, x_{22}\}$	$\{x_2, x_6 - x_{15}, x_{17}, x_{22}\}$
x_5	1	$\{x_1 - x_4, x_6 - x_{25}\}$	$\{x_1 - x_4, x_6 - x_{25}\}$	$\{x_1 - x_4, x_6 - x_{25}\}$	$\{x_1 - x_4, x_6 - x_{15}, x_{17}, x_{22}\}$	$\{x_1 - x_4, x_6 - x_{15}, x_{17}, x_{22}\}$
x_6	8	$\{x_9 - x_{25}\}$	$\{x_9 - x_{25}\}$	$\{x_9 - x_{25}\}$	$\{x_9 - x_{15}, x_{22}\}$	$\{x_9 - x_{23}\}$
x_7	6	$\{x_6, x_8, x_{19} - x_{25}\}$	$\{x_6, x_8, x_{19} - x_{25}\}$	$\{x_6, x_8, x_{19} - x_{25}\}$	$\{x_6, x_8, x_{17}, x_{20}, x_{22}\}$	$\{x_6, x_8, x_9 - x_{23}\}$
x_8	7	$\{x_6, x_9 - x_{25}\}$	$\{x_6, x_9 - x_{25}\}$	$\{x_6, x_9 - x_{25}\}$	$\{x_6, x_9 - x_{23}\}$	$\{x_6, x_9 - x_{23}\}$
x_9	10	$\{x_{10} - x_{25}\}$	$\{x_{10} - x_{25}\}$	$\{x_{10} - x_{25}\}$	$\{x_{10} - x_{23}\}$	$\{x_{10} - x_{23}\}$
x_{10}	12	$\{x_{13} - x_{25}\}$	$\{x_{13} - x_{25}\}$	$\{x_{13} - x_{25}\}$	$\{x_{13} - x_{23}\}$	$\{x_{13} - x_{23}\}$
x_{11}	9	$\{x_9, x_{10}, x_{12} - x_{25}\}$	$\{x_9, x_{10}, x_{12} - x_{25}\}$	$\{x_9, x_{10}, x_{12} - x_{25}\}$	$\{x_9 - x_{23}\}$	$\{x_9 - x_{23}\}$
x_{12}	11	$\{x_{10}, x_{13} - x_{25}\}$	$\{x_{10}, x_{13} - x_{25}\}$	$\{x_{10}, x_{13} - x_{25}\}$	$\{x_{10}, x_{13} - x_{23}\}$	$\{x_{10}, x_{13} - x_{25}\}$
x_{13}	13	$\{x_{14} - x_{25}\}$	$\{x_{14} - x_{25}\}$	$\{x_{14} - x_{25}\}$	$\{x_{14} - x_{23}\}$	$\{x_{14} - x_{23}\}$
x_{14}	17	$\{x_{16}, x_{18} - x_{21}, x_{23} - x_{25}\}$	$\{x_{16}, x_{18} - x_{21}, x_{23} - x_{25}\}$	$\{x_{16}, x_{18} - x_{21}, x_{23} - x_{25}\}$	$\{x_{16}, x_{18} - x_{21}, x_{23}\}$	$\{x_{16}, x_{18} - x_{21}, x_{23}\}$
x_{15}	15	$\{x_{14}, x_{16}, x_{18} - x_{25}\}$	$\{x_{14}, x_{16}, x_{18} - x_{25}\}$	$\{x_{14}, x_{16}, x_{18} - x_{25}\}$	$\{x_{14}, x_{16}, x_{18} - x_{23}\}$	$\{x_{14}, x_{16}, x_{18} - x_{23}\}$
x_{16}	18	$\{x_{18} - x_{21}, x_{23} - x_{25}\}$	$\{x_{18} - x_{21}, x_{23} - x_{25}\}$	$\{x_{18} - x_{21}, x_{23} - x_{25}\}$	$\{x_{18} - x_{21}, x_{23}, x_{24}\}$	$\{x_{18} - x_{21}, x_{23}, x_{24}\}$
x_{17}	14	$\{x_{14} - x_{16}, x_{18} - x_{25}\}$	$\{x_{14} - x_{16}, x_{18} - x_{25}\}$	$\{x_{14} - x_{16}, x_{18} - x_{25}\}$	$\{x_{14} - x_{16}, x_{18} - x_{24}\}$	$\{x_{14} - x_{16}, x_{18} - x_{23}\}$
x_{18}	22	$\{x_{19}, x_{24}, x_{25}\}$	$\{x_{19}, x_{24}, x_{25}\}$	$\{x_{19}, x_{24}, x_{25}\}$	$\{x_{19}, x_{24}\}$	$\{x_{19}, x_{24}\}$
x_{19}	23	$\{x_{24}, x_{25}\}$	$\{x_{24}, x_{25}\}$	$\{x_{24}, x_{25}\}$	$\{x_{24}\}$	$\{x_{24}\}$
x_{20}	19	$\{x_{18}, x_{19}, x_{21}, x_{23} - x_{25}\}$	$\{x_{18}, x_{19}, x_{21}, x_{23} - x_{25}\}$	$\{x_{18}, x_{19}, x_{21}, x_{23} - x_{25}\}$	$\{x_{18}, x_{19}, x_{21}, x_{23}, x_{24}\}$	$\{x_{18}, x_{19}, x_{21}, x_{23}, x_{24}\}$
x_{21}	20	$\{x_{18}, x_{19}, x_{23} - x_{25}\}$	$\{x_{18}, x_{19}, x_{23} - x_{25}\}$	$\{x_{18}, x_{19}, x_{23} - x_{25}\}$	$\{x_{18}, x_{19}, x_{23}, x_{24}\}$	$\{x_{18}, x_{19}, x_{23}, x_{24}\}$
x_{22}	16	$\{x_{14}, x_{16}, x_{18} - x_{21}, x_{23} - x_{25}\}$	$\{x_{14}, x_{16}, x_{18} - x_{21}, x_{23} - x_{25}\}$	$\{x_{14}, x_{16}, x_{18} - x_{21}, x_{23} - x_{25}\}$	$\{x_{14}, x_{16}, x_{18} - x_{21}, x_{23}, x_{24}\}$	$\{x_{14}, x_{16}, x_{18} - x_{21}, x_{23}, x_{24}\}$
x_{23}	21	$\{x_{18}, x_{19}, x_{24}, x_{25}\}$	$\{x_{18}, x_{19}, x_{24}, x_{25}\}$	$\{x_{18}, x_{19}, x_{24}, x_{25}\}$	$\{x_{18}, x_{19}, x_{21}, x_{24}\}$	$\{x_{18}, x_{19}, x_{24}, x_{25}\}$
x_{24}	24	$\{x_{25}\}$	$\{x_{25}\}$	$\{x_{25}\}$	$\{x_{25}\}$	$\{x_{25}\}$
x_{25}	25	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA

* NA: no alternative found

no achievable alternative. Table IV provides the decision maker with an overview of the degradation of the ranking order of the target alternative under a deterioration of the considered alternatives' performance with respect to the criteria.

- which alternatives' ranks are achievable by upgrading the current rating of an alternative under a specific criterion based on the restricted condition described in Proposition 1? Similarly, we implement **Algorithm 4** with the maximum value of the closeness coefficient information extracted from Table III repeatedly over the rating of each alternative for different criteria. The results are listed in Table V. As x_5 is the best alternative, there is no higher rank achievable alternative for it under any criterion. Performance improvement wise, Table V provides a spectrum of how the current ranking order of the target alternatives could improve with the improvement of the performance of that alternative under different criteria. The universities would also receive useful information, namely, how improving the performance through a criterion would yield a better rank position than the current one.

Table V: Achievable higher rank alternatives with a change in attributes

x_i	$\mathcal{A}_{i1}^>$	$\mathcal{A}_{i2}^>$	$\mathcal{A}_{i3}^>$	$\mathcal{A}_{i4}^>$	$\mathcal{A}_{i5}^>$
x_1	$\{x_3, x_5\}$	NA	NA	$\{x_3, x_5\}$	NA
x_2	$\{x_1, x_3 - x_5\}$	NA	NA	$\{x_1, x_3 - x_5\}$	NA
x_3	$\{x_5\}$	NA	NA	NA	$\{x_5\}$
x_4	$\{x_1, x_3, x_5\}$	NA	NA	$\{x_1, x_3, x_5\}$	$\{x_1\}$
x_5	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
x_6	$\{x_2, x_4, x_7, x_8\}$	$\{x_8\}$	NA	$\{x_1, x_2, x_4, x_7, x_8\}$	$\{x_8\}$
x_7	$\{x_1 - x_4\}$	NA	NA	$\{x_1, x_2, x_4\}$	NA
x_8	$\{x_1 - x_5, x_7\}$	$\{x_7, x_{11}\}$	NA	$\{x_7\}$	NA
x_9	$\{x_6, x_8, x_{11}\}$	$\{x_{11}\}$	NA	$\{x_6 - x_8, x_{11}\}$	$\{x_{11}\}$
x_{10}	$\{x_1 - x_9, x_{11}, x_{12}\}$	$\{x_9, x_{11}, x_{12}\}$	$\{x_9, x_{12}\}$	$\{x_9, x_{11}, x_{12}\}$	NA
x_{11}	$\{x_6 - x_8\}$	NA	NA	$\{x_6 - x_8\}$	$\{x_6 - x_8\}$
x_{12}	$\{x_9, x_{11}\}$	$\{x_9, x_{11}\}$	NA	$\{x_6, x_8, x_9, x_{11}\}$	$\{x_9, x_{11}\}$
x_{13}	$\{x_1 - x_{12}, x_{14}, x_{15}\}$	$\{x_9 - x_{11}\}$	NA	NA	$\{x_9 - x_{12}\}$
x_{14}	$\{x_9 - x_{13}, x_{15}, x_{17}, x_{22}\}$	$\{x_9 - x_{13}, x_{15}, x_{17}, x_{22}\}$	NA	$\{x_9 - x_{13}, x_{15}, x_{17}, x_{22}\}$	$\{x_{15}, x_{22}\}$
x_{15}	$\{x_6, x_8 - x_{13}, x_{17}\}$	$\{x_9, x_{10}, x_{12}, x_{13}, x_{17}\}$	NA	$\{x_9 - x_{13}, x_{17}\}$	$\{x_{10}, x_{12}, x_{13}, x_{17}\}$
x_{16}	$\{x_6, x_8 - x_{15}, x_{17}, x_{22}\}$	$\{x_{14}, x_{15}, x_{22}\}$	NA	$\{x_{14}, x_{15}, x_{17}, x_{22}\}$	NA
x_{17}	$\{x_6, x_8 - x_{13}\}$	$\{x_6, x_8 - x_{13}, x_{15}\}$	NA	NA	$\{x_9, x_{10}, x_{12}, x_{13}\}$
x_{18}	$\{x_9, x_{10}, x_{12} - x_{17}, x_{20} - x_{23}\}$	$\{x_{14} - x_{16}, x_{20} - x_{23}\}$	NA	$\{x_{14} - x_{17}, x_{20} - x_{23}\}$	$\{x_{16}, x_{20} - x_{23}\}$
x_{19}	$\{x_9 - x_{18}, x_{20} - x_{23}\}$	$\{x_{16}, x_{18}, x_{20} - x_{23}\}$	$\{x_{18}, x_{23}\}$	$\{x_{14} - x_{18}, x_{20} - x_{23}\}$	$\{x_{18}, x_{21}, x_{23}\}$
x_{20}	$\{x_2, x_6 - x_{17}, x_{22}\}$	$\{x_{14} - x_{16}, x_{22}\}$	$\{x_{16}\}$	$\{x_{16}\}$	$\{x_{14}, x_{16}x_{22}\}$
x_{21}	$\{x_9 - x_{17}, x_{20}, x_{22}\}$	$\{x_{14}, x_{16}, x_{20}, x_{22}\}$	NA	$\{x_{14} - x_{16}, x_{20}, x_{22}\}$	$\{x_{16}, x_{22}\}$
x_{22}	$\{x_6 - x_{13}, x_{15}, x_{17}\}$	$\{x_{10}, x_{12}, x_{13}, x_{15}, x_{17}, x_{21}\}$	$\{x_{13}, x_{15}, x_{17}\}$	$\{x_{15}, x_{17}\}$	NA
x_{23}	$\{x_9 - x_{17}, x_{20} - x_{22}\}$	$\{x_{14} - x_{16}, x_{20} - x_{22}\}$	$\{x_{21}, x_{22}\}$	$\{x_{14} - x_{16}, x_{20} - x_{22}\}$	$\{21\}$
x_{24}	$\{x_6, x_8 - x_{23}\}$	NA	NA	NA	NA
x_{25}	$\{x_{16}, x_{18} - x_{21}, x_{23}, x_{24}\}$	$\{x_{16}, x_{18} - x_{21}, x_{23}, x_{24}\}$	NA	$\{x_{24}\}$	NA

* NA: no alternative found

Tables I-V allow us to address specific questions related to any scenario concerning a target alternative. For example,

- is it possible for x_4 to achieve the rank of x_5 ? We can answer this question from Tables I-V. From Table I, x_5 has a higher rank than x_4 . Further, Table V confirms that x_4 can achieve the rank of x_5 by upgrading its rating either under criterion C_1 or C_4 . Put simply, we can achieve the rank of x_5 by changing the ratings in the set of criteria $\mathcal{C}_{54} = \{C_1, C_4\}$. How much change in C_1 or C_4 of alternative

x_4 is required to achieve the ranking? By implementing **Algorithm 1**, we obtain $\Delta_{41} = 4.8998$ and $\Delta_{44} = 12.2965$ (taking $\epsilon = 0.0001$). One may note that criterion C_1 requires a smaller change to achieve the rank of x_5 than criterion C_5 . Therefore, to manipulate the rank of x_4 , it is better for the decision maker to change the rating of x_4 under C_1 .

- find the set of alternatives which has the potential of becoming as the best alternative by changing its rating under any criterion? To answer this question, we need to search the collection of sets $\mathcal{A}_{ij}^>$ for $i \in \{1, 2, \dots, 25\} \setminus \{5\}$, and $j = 1, \dots, 5$. Therefore, we scan through Table V for x_5 . For a fixed i , if $x_5 \in \mathcal{A}_{i1}^> \cup \mathcal{A}_{i2}^> \cup \mathcal{A}_{i3}^> \cup \mathcal{A}_{i4}^> \cup \mathcal{A}_{i5}^>$, then x_i could emerge as the best alternative. From Table V, we obtain the desirable set of alternatives $\{x_1, x_2, x_3, x_4, x_8, x_{10}, x_{13}\}$.
- is it possible to reverse the rank order of a pair of alternatives without affecting the other alternatives ranking? Consider the pair of alternatives (x_5, x_4) . From Table I, $r(x_5) = 1$ and $r(x_4) = 4$. Therefore, to reverse the rank order of (x_5, x_4) , we need to upgrade x_4 's ratings and to downgrade x_1 's rating under a specified criterion. From Table IV and V, we note that x_4 can achieve x_5 's rank by upgrading its rating under the criteria $\{C_1, C_4\}$ while x_5 can switch to x_4 's ranking by downgrading its rating under the criteria $\{C_1, C_2, C_3, C_4, C_5\}$. The concept 'reversing ranking order' is taken to mean that the new closeness coefficient of x_5 and x_4 will $CC_5^{new} = CC_4$ and $CC_4^{new} = CC_5$ while the rest of the alternatives' closeness coefficient remain unaltered. There are $5 \times 2 = 10$ ways to reverse the rating of the pair (x_5, x_4) by changing their ratings under different sets of criteria. The required change in the ratings under different pairs of criteria are found using **Algorithm 1**, and are listed in Table VI. We

Table VI: Changes required in the alternatives for reversing the ranking order

Scenario	x_5		x_4	
	Criteria	Change	Criteria	Change
1	C_1	$\Delta_{51}^4 = -2.9302$	C_1	$\Delta_{41}^5 = 4.8998$
2	C_1	$\Delta_{51}^4 = -2.9302$	C_4	$\Delta_{44}^5 = 12.2965$
3	C_2	$\Delta_{52}^4 = -3.9559$	C_1	$\Delta_{41}^5 = 4.8998$
4	C_2	$\Delta_{52}^4 = -3.9559$	C_4	$\Delta_{44}^5 = 12.2965$
5	C_3	$\Delta_{53}^4 = -12.9070$	C_1	$\Delta_{41}^5 = 4.8998$
6	C_3	$\Delta_{53}^4 = -12.9070$	C_4	$\Delta_{44}^5 = 12.2965$
7	C_4	$\Delta_{54}^4 = -18.5134$	C_1	$\Delta_{41}^5 = 4.8998$
8	C_4	$\Delta_{54}^4 = -18.5134$	C_4	$\Delta_{44}^5 = 12.2965$
9	C_5	$\Delta_{55}^4 = -18.0546$	C_1	$\Delta_{41}^5 = 4.8998$
10	C_5	$\Delta_{55}^4 = -18.0546$	C_4	$\Delta_{44}^5 = 12.2965$

note that the rating of x_5 under criteria C_1 and C_2 requires less change than criteria $\{C_3, C_4, C_5\}$ to achieve the rank of alternative x_4 while x_4 requires a smaller change under criterion C_1 than C_4 .

7. Conclusion

In this study, we have considered the sensitivity and robustness analysis of the recommendations from a TOPSIS based decision making model and provided a framework which we refer to as the post factum

analysis of TOPSIS. We have assumed that only the decision information is vulnerable to change and the rest of the information and parameters are fixed in the course of the post factum analysis of TOPSIS. To understand the dynamics of a change of the decision information, we have analyzed the effect of a change in the rating of an alternative under a criterion and established the appropriate condition to predict the effect on the closeness coefficient. To determine how much change is required in an alternative's rating under a criterion to obtain a higher ranked alternative's ranking position, we have derived conditions based on the solution of the quadratic inequality. As alternative A can achieve alternative B 's rank by changing some or all of the criteria from the criteria set C , we have developed an algorithm to find the reachable set of criteria for alternative A to obtain the rank of alternative B . We have also investigated the nature of the closeness coefficient of an alternative with respect to the change in that alternative's rating under a criterion. The non-decreasing nature of the closeness coefficient allowed us to identify the bounds of the closeness coefficient of an alternative. Based on the bounds of the closeness coefficient, two algorithms are proposed to identify the upper- and lower-rank achievable alternatives. With the above information in hand, we then proposed a rank reversing method for a pair of alternatives, without affecting the other alternatives' ranking positions. Finally, using the universities ranking problem, we have illustrated various strategic manipulation scenarios.

Although our study provides a new post factum analysis framework to the TOPSIS based decision making model, some limitations exist. In our analysis, we have considered variations albeit for a single input information. Considering the variations in multiple inputs and analyzing the TOPSIS model is challenging. Further, the validity of our results depends on the normalization techniques used; specifically, it is valid for the linear scale transformation. These limitations could be taken up as future research opportunities in understanding the minimal performance change needed for improvement (Hyde & Maier, 2006; Hyde et al., 2005; Kadziński et al., 2016). Finally, it will be interesting to investigate the post factum analysis of decision information in TOPSIS under an uncertain environment, where the ratings of the alternatives against the criteria are expressed as fuzzy numbers, intuitionistic fuzzy sets, hesitant fuzzy set, Pythagorean fuzzy set, and so on.

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